

Received 15 October 2025, accepted 28 October 2025, date of publication 3 November 2025, date of current version 12 November 2025.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3628066

RESEARCH ARTICLE

FL-MU: A Benchmark Dataset for Federated Intrusion Detection in IoT Networks

LINTHOINGAMBI TAKHELLAMBAM¹, URIKHIMBAM BOBY CLINTON¹, NAZRUL HOQUE¹, KHUMUKCHAM ROBINDRO SINGH¹, AND MONOWAR BHUYAN², (Senior Member, IEEE)

¹Department of Computer Science, Manipur University, Canchipur, Imphal, Manipur 795003, India

²Department of Computing Science, Umeå University, 901 87 Umeå, Sweden

Corresponding author: Nazrul Hoque (tonazrul@gmail.com)

This work was supported in part by European Commission through the Horizon Europe Project SovereignEdge.COGNIT under Grant 101092711; and in part by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation through the Wallenberg AI, Autonomous Systems and Software Program (WASP).

ABSTRACT Due to the tremendous deployment of sensors, actuators, and remote devices, Internet of Things (IoT) networks have gained popularity across a wide range of application domains. As a result, the number of attackers and the dynamics of IoT network attacks are also increasing proportionately. Moreover, IoT networks generate a huge amount of sensitive data that must be carefully protected to prevent potential exploitation and exploration by adversaries. The advent of Federated Learning (FL) paved the way for enhancing data privacy and security of IoT data. Although several FL-based security systems have been developed for IoT networks, many lack effectiveness and efficiency. This limitation is due to the unavailability of up-to-date benchmark IoT network intrusion datasets that accurately reflect real-world IoT network traffic, encompassing a wide range of IoT protocols and recent, diverse attack types. This discrepancy significantly hinders the development, validation, and comparative evaluation of existing security solutions. To meet this critical need, we develop a practical IoT network intrusion dataset called FL-MU using client-specific IoT network testbeds. Each client testbed comprises more than 30 devices communicating over seven different IoT communication protocols. The FL-MU dataset includes eleven types of attacks, comprising over 19 million instances with 121 features. The effectiveness of the dataset is established on multiple state-of-the-art FL-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs). The FL-based IDSs exhibits superior performance when trained on our FL-MU dataset as compared to other existing datasets. This highlights the quality and suitability of the developed FL-MU dataset for training robust and accurate FL-based security systems. The FL-MU dataset and the related implementation codes are made available at the Kaggle repository: <https://doi.org/10.34740/kaggle/dsv/13106381>, contributing to the research community for the advancement of IoT security.

INDEX TERMS Federated learning, Internet of Things, intrusion detection system, IoT dataset, cybersecurity.

I. INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of the Internet of Things (IoT) around the globe is a thriving target of cyber attackers to steal sensitive data, conduct financial theft, and other malicious acts that disrupt the services provided by the network. Despite its inherent vulnerabilities caused by resource-constrained IoT devices, the use of IoT technology

is exponentially increasing in industries, agriculture, and the healthcare sectors [1]. However, the end users and manufacturers often ignore these vulnerabilities due to a lack of security awareness and the resource-constrained nature of the device, which makes it easier to compromise the IoT systems. Such breaches can result in severe consequences in the real applications domain that might lead to identity theft, significant financial losses, misdiagnosis of chronic diseases, failures in smart transportation systems, etc.

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Tony Thomas.

The attackers use various tools and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) such as Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) to breach data privacy, and compromise security, such as hacking of smart home objects, tracking users' personal activities, modification of machinery settings in the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), IoT device hijacking, and formation of IoT botnets [2]. Despite these vulnerabilities, it is becoming increasingly difficult to envision a society without IoT technology. Moreover, our dependence on IoT technologies has significantly expanded over the past several years. This reliance necessitates the development of sustainable solutions to address the associated security challenges.

In the literature, we found a good number of Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) that can detect and prevent different types of attacks on IoT networks. The IDSs analyze network traffic characteristics and identify malicious network behaviors. The network security researchers and practitioners use different techniques, such as Statistical Learning, Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), and Multiview-Multitask Learning during network traffic analysis [3]. ML/DL-based IDSs have gained popularity due to their effectiveness and efficiency. However, DL-based IDSs are found to be more effective due to automatic feature engineering compared to other counterparts [4].

The ML/DL-based IDSs require an abundant amount of data that is comprehensive, precise, and able to represent the real-time network scenarios to train IDSs, ensuring optimal performance in detecting network attacks. However, most of the existing ML/DL-based IDSs are inefficient in detecting recent attacks on IoT networks. This limitation is primarily due to the lack of availability of datasets that capture recent and up-to-date attack scenarios as well as diverse IoT network behaviours. Therefore, exposing the IDS model to a wide range of datasets containing correct labels of the instance, adequate attack and legitimate traffic patterns, large volume and value, is still lacking in the literature [5]. This can impact the validation of the state-of-the-art IDSs in identifying recent IoT network attacks. Additionally, the ML/DL-based IDS lacks concern for data privacy preservation, which is a trending issue, especially in sensitive application areas of IoT such as smart healthcare, smart home, industrial systems, banking, etc [6]. To address this privacy concern, FL has emerged as a promising solution [7]. In Federated Learning (FL), each participating client's model is trained on its own data without sharing the data with a centralized server. Multiple IoT networks are used as clients, and they work collaboratively to train a global model. Since data is not shared among the clients during federated training, it ensures data privacy.

Each client performs local training on its own data and shares only the model parameters with a centralized server. This centralized server aggregates the parameters received from the clients and updates the global model. FL not only ensures data privacy, but it also significantly reduces computational complexity. Moreover, the FL technique can

effectively address data storage challenges, improve the IDS's ability to generalize across diverse IoT network traffic behaviours and varying attack traffic patterns. Therefore, there is a pressing need for a realistic FL-based IoT network intrusion dataset that can fuel the development of a robust FL-based IDS.

In the real-world scenario, the protocols used by IoT networks are not always confined to the well-known MQTT and CoAP protocols. Rather, IoT uses different protocols such as AMQP, DDS, SOAP, STOMP, and WebSocket during communications. Most existing IoT network intrusion datasets are generated considering the MQTT communication protocol only. As a result, they often overlook subtle but significant attacks. This diversity is quite essential to ensure that the IDS can effectively recognize and respond to a broad spectrum of potential threats, reflecting real-world scenarios. However, none of the existing IoT network intrusion datasets include these diverse protocols and attack scenarios. The lack of protocol-specific IoT attack traffic datasets creates a major setback in developing and validating an effective IDS for IoT networks.

This motivates us to create the FL-MU dataset, encompassing multiple IoT communication protocols and a good number of attack types, including recent attack scenarios. We believe the dataset would be a milestone for IoT network security experts and researchers in validating new IDSs. In addition, the dataset can be used to establish the effectiveness and efficiency of FL-based IDSs with data privacy and security. The dataset is created from our own laboratory testbed, which is scalable in terms of IoT devices, communication protocols, attack types, and volume of traffic generated from the testbed. Moreover, the FL approach is employed in this work to establish the validation of a robust FL-based IDS using our FL-MU dataset. FL enables collaborative training of an IDS to learn diverse attack patterns across multiple clients in a privacy-preserving manner, enhancing its generalizability and robustness. Each participating client executes an IDS in a federated environment to protect its data while contributing to updating the global model. Although thousands of clients typically participate in real-world scenarios, we utilized only three clients to create a simplified environment with limited resources. This setup facilitates detailed examination of attack patterns and the model's behavior during validation. Our objective is to establish that the FL-based IDS can efficiently operate on our FL-MU dataset by accurately detecting diverse attack patterns and exhibiting robust performance.

A. NOVELTY AND CONTRIBUTIONS

The novelty of the work is the creation of a realistic, scalable, and comprehensive IoT network intrusion dataset incorporating multiple attack scenarios from our own IoT network testbed. The dataset is created in a closed environment set up without revealing any sensitive information of the client's network. Unlike the existing datasets, our dataset includes multiple IoT communication protocols, such as Advanced

Message Queue Protocol (AMQP), Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP), Data Distribution Service (DDS), Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol, Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP), Simple Text Oriented Messaging Protocol (STOMP), and WebSocket. Moreover, our dataset includes various protocol-specific, state-of-the-art IoT network attacks, such as Slowite, Sinkhole attack, Sybil attack, and Selective forwarding attack, along with traditional flooding and MQTT-based attacks. Additionally, the FL-MU dataset has a better scope for FL researchers to develop security systems for IoT networks.

The novelty of the work is established with the following notable contributions.

- 1) Development of an IoT network testbed comprising more than 30 IoT devices. The testbed is scalable in nature and can generate an enormous IoT network traffic with diverse attack patterns.
- 2) Creation of an IoT network intrusion dataset known as FL-MU, which is preprocessed and labeled accordingly.
- 3) The FL-MU dataset comprises multiple state-of-the-art attack types, viz., TCP synchronization flooding attack, MQTT connection flooding attack, Slowite attack, AMQP flooding attack, STOMP flooding attack, SOAP flooding attack, DNS amplification attack, Man-in-the-Middle (MiTM) attack, Selective forwarding attack, Sinkhole attack, and Sybil attack.
- 4) The dataset includes IoT network traffic patterns considering most of the standard IoT communication protocols, such as AMQP, CoAP, DDS, MQTT, SOAP, STOMP, and WebSocket.
- 5) The usability of the dataset is established through experimental evidence, such that network security researchers can use our dataset to develop effective IDSs for IoT network security.

B. IMPORTANCE OF FL-MU DATASET

In recent days, many new variants of IoT vulnerabilities have emerged, which are mostly generated through IoT botnets. The existing IoT datasets available in the literature did not include the recent botnet-based IoT attack scenarios. Besides, the existing IoT intrusion datasets contain network traffic either from a simulated or an emulated network environment. Only a few IoT network intrusion datasets are generated from a physical IoT network testbed, where recent attacks are launched on some physical IoT devices with new IoT protocols. But, in real-life applications, attackers target resource-constrained IoT devices to launch various attacks directly or use them to form a large botnet. This issue creates a gap for the existing FL-based IDSs in validating their effectiveness in identifying the attack types. Moreover, existing datasets fail to include recent attack scenarios such as Sinkhole attacks and Slowite DDoS attacks. Therefore, it is essential to generate an effective IoT intrusion dataset that incorporates protocol-specific IoT network traffic, with the latest attack types. In addition, existing datasets are mostly

generated from a simulated IoT network testbed. This leads to the failure of capturing the real IoT network behaviours. Hence, the existing IDSs are not robust in identifying the attacks. Consequently, there is a need for a dataset that effectively addresses the aforementioned limitations. To this end, the FL-MU dataset provides a comprehensive solution. The FL-MU dataset contains network traffic collected from physical IoT devices as well as source-emulated IoT devices. It includes network traffic behaviour of seven IoT communication protocols and eleven protocol-specific attacks on IoT devices. Thus, the comprehensive nature of the FL-MU dataset makes a profoundly advantageous contribution to the development of a robust and effective IDS for IoT networks. It also addresses the existing gap in the literature regarding the shortage of up-to-date IoT network intrusion data.

C. ORGANIZATION

The paper includes five sections that are organized as follows. Section II summarizes the related works, i.e., existing IoT datasets, and a comparison of our FL-MU dataset with the existing counterparts. The core functionalities of the FL-MU dataset generation framework are elaborated in Section III. The experimental evaluation, including the exploratory data analysis, data preprocessing, implementation details of the Federated Learning models on our FL-MU dataset, and performance evaluation, is discussed in Section IV. Finally, Section V gives the concluding remarks, followed by outlining the future directions of our work.

II. RELATED WORK

Existing IoT network intrusion datasets found in the literature primarily focused on DoS, DDoS, MiTM, password cracking, and Ransomware attacks at different layers of IoT. Additionally, only a few papers have explored the use of CoAP and Modbus protocols [8], [9], [10]. However, there is a lack of exploration on sophisticated IoT network attacks such as Sinkhole, Sybil, and Selective forwarding attacks. Moreover, researchers leverage simulation tools such as COOJA, Common Open Research Emulator (CORE), IoTflock, Node-Red, and Ostinato to simulate IoT network intrusion datasets, instead of a real physical IoT testbed [11]. In the literature, we found eleven recent and commonly used IoT network intrusion datasets, i.e., Bot-IoT [11], ToN_IoT [12], Edge-IIoTset [13], DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT [14], FLNet2023 [15], CICIoT2023 [16], CICIoMT2024 [17], UOS_IOTSH_2024 [18], Farm-flow [19], MU-IoT [9], and NIMS IoT attack [20]. A brief summary of the existing datasets and their limitations is discussed next.

- **Bot-IoT:** Koroniotis et al. [11] generated this dataset in a simulated IoT testbed utilizing the Node-Red and Ostinato tools at the UNSW Canberra laboratory. The authors used the MQTT protocol exclusively to communicate among the IoT devices. The Bot-IoT¹ dataset consists of 46 flow features and 10 attack types,

¹<https://research.unsw.edu.au/projects/bot-iot-dataset>

including Service scanning, OS fingerprinting, TCP SYN attack, DoS/DDoS, UDP flooding DoS/DDoS, HTTP flooding DoS/DDoS, keylogging, and Data theft. Although it includes three types of DDoS attacks, it does not cover MQTT protocol-specific DDoS attacks, such as MQTT connect flooding. This is a limitation of the Bot-IoT dataset. Moreover, the Bot-IoT dataset fails to fully capture the diverse attack patterns observed in real-world IoT scenarios. The dataset is found suitable for various purposes, including evaluation of IDS [21], [22], developing feature selection methods for attack traffic identification [23], detecting information theft attacks [24], and DDoS attacks in Smart City IoT environments [25].

- **TON_IoT:** Alsaedi et al. [12] created this dataset from a hybrid IoT testbed setup in the UNSW Canberra cybersecurity lab. The testbed consists of a physical setup with 7 IoT/IIoT devices and 6 simulated IoT devices. The traffic generated in the testbed includes both legitimate and attack traffic, with 9 attack variants. The attacks incorporated in the TON_IoT² dataset include MiTM, Cross-site Scripting, Scanning, Password cracking, DoS, Backdoor attacks, Ransomware attacks, DDoS, and Data injection attacks. In addition to the most commonly used MQTT protocol, the authors include traffic generated from the Modbus protocol. The TON_IoT dataset contains 22 features derived from the raw IoT network traffic. However, this dataset lacks other IoT communication protocols and recent IoT attacks. In the literature, this dataset has been used to evaluate IDS of IoT and vehicular ad-hoc networks [10], [26], [27].
- **Edge-IIoTset:** Ferrag et al. [13] created the Edge-IIoTset³ dataset from a realistic IoT/IIoT testbed consisting of 7 layers, i.e., Perception layer, edge layer, software-defined networking layer, fog layer, blockchain layer, network functions virtualization layer, and cloud computing layers. The testbed includes 13 IoT/IIoT sensor devices, with MQTT and Modbus protocols for generating the IoT/IIoT network traffic. The dataset includes 5 attack categories, viz., malware attacks, MiTM attacks, injection attacks, DoS/DDoS attacks, and information-gathering attacks. These attack categories are further divided into 14 distinct attack types. Additionally, the authors employed the Zeek and TShark tools to extract 1176 features from the raw IoT/IIoT network traffic, out of which 61 best features are selected. However, this work focuses on the widely used MQTT and Modbus protocols, thus exhibiting limited variability in attack patterns. In previous studies, this dataset has been used to develop IDSs for IoT networks [28], [29].

- **DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT:** This dataset was created by Alatram et al. [14] from an IoT testbed consisting of 36 hardware devices to improve the detection of MQTT Protocol-based attacks. The malicious traffic is obtained from launching the DoS/DDoS attacks through CONNECT Flooding Attack, Delayed CONNECT Flooding Attack, Invalid Subscription Flooding Attack, CONNECT Flooding with WILL Payload Attack, and TCP SYN Flooding Attack. This dataset is not publicly available. Notably, the dataset lacks representation of Slowite flooding attacks, a type of denial-of-service attack associated with the MQTT protocol. This dataset has been used in developing an FL-based anomaly detection in IoT [30].
- **FLNet2023:** Kumar et al. [15] created a conventional network intrusion dataset called FLNet2023⁴ that includes DoS, DDoS, and web-based attacks, including SQL Command Injection, Cross-site scripting (XSS), and Web SQL Injection, as well as MiTM attack. The dataset was generated in a simulated network environment using the CORE tool, which limits its ability to represent real-world traffic scenarios. Moreover, this work lacks exploration of the IoT network traffic, which is a critical focus in current research. Additionally, the authors confined their experiments to the FedAvg algorithm without validating some advanced Federated Learning techniques, such as FedProx or FedSGD, on their dataset.
- **CICIoT2023:** Neto et al. [16] created the CICIoT2023⁵ dataset from an IoT testbed consisting of 105 devices. This dataset includes 33 attack types which belong to seven attack categories, viz., DDoS, DoS, Recon, Web-based, Bruteforce, spoofing, and Mirai attacks on IoT devices. The quality of the dataset is validated solely using ML models, lacking evaluation on FL-based IDS, which are inherently privacy-preserving. This dataset is being widely used for developing anomaly detection systems and IDSs in securing IoT networks [31], [32].
- **CICIoMT2024:** Dadkhah et al. [17] generated the CICIoMT2024⁶ dataset using a hybrid physical and simulated testbed, using the IoTFlock tool. The authors focused exclusively on three communication technologies, such as MQTT, Wi-Fi, and Bluetooth, for launching attacks, thereby omitting other widely used IoT communication protocols. The dataset includes only five categories of attacks, viz. DoS, DDoS, Recon, MQTT, and Spoofing. Notably, the authors did not consider attacks based on the CoAP protocol, which is commonly employed in Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) applications. Furthermore, the study does not incorporate any evaluation of FL-based IDS.

²<https://research.unsw.edu.au/projects/toniot-datasets>

³ <http://iee-dataport.org/8939>

⁴<https://github.com/nsol-nmsu/FML-Network>

⁵<https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/iotdataset-2023.html>

⁶<https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/iomt-dataset-2024.html>

- **UOS_IOTSH_2024:** Omar et al. [18] introduced the UOS_IOTSH_2024⁷ dataset, primarily for Sinkhole routing attack. This dataset is introduced to address the significant gap in the existing datasets that lack the patterns of Sinkhole attacks in IoT networks. The authors utilize the COOJA simulator to simulate a real-world IoT environment and simulate the Sinkhole attacks by executing the attack on the RPL⁸ IoT network over the IPV6 network layer. The UOS_IOTSH_2024 dataset provides a detailed representation of RPL IoT network behaviour under both legitimate and Sinkhole attack conditions. It includes 13 extracted features that characterize the network's performance and response to the presence of Sinkhole attacks. This dataset has been used in mitigating the black-hole attacks in IoT [33].
- **Farm-flow:** Ferreira et al. [19] introduced an agriculture-based IoT intrusion dataset named the Farm-flow⁹ dataset that aims to enhance the IDS for agricultural IoT networks. This dataset was generated from a greenhouse environment, where 3 microcontrollers and 7 distinct IoT sensors were strategically deployed in specific zones. Additionally, the authors incorporated several actuators that are triggered by stimuli from the microcontrollers, enabling automated responses within the system. The IoT network traffic was generated using the MQTT, CoAP, and HTTP protocols. The Farm-flow dataset includes 8 attack types, such as Port scanning, Botnet DDoS, TCP SYN flooding, HTTP flooding, MQTT flooding, ICMP flooding, UDP flooding, and ARP spoofing attacks, which were executed by different attacking tools. This dataset has more than 1 million instances and 101 flow features. However, this dataset lacks the presentation of other IoT communication protocols and recent attacks.
- **MU-IoT:** Clinton and Hoque [9] created the recent IoT dataset named MU-IoT,¹⁰ which is generated from an IoT smart lab application at Manipur University, India. It included network traffic patterns for both legitimate and attack scenarios. The dataset includes a good number of IoT attacks, such as Scanning attacks, Password hacking, Injection, MiTM, Spyware attacks, and DoS/DDoS flooding attacks. However, the dataset does not include recent attacks such as Sinkhole, Selective forwarding, and Sybil attacks. Moreover, it lacks network traffic data from IoT communication protocols like DDS and SOAP.
- **NIMS IoT attack:** Adjei et al. [20] developed the NIMS LAB IoT Attack Dataset 2025-1 [34], which includes four categories of IoT-focused attacks, viz. Portscan, Slowloris, SYN Flood, and Vulnerability Scan. These attacks are conducted on nine different IoT devices. The

dataset did not incorporate any data privacy-preserving mechanisms, such as FL, nor explored the potential applicability of FL. Furthermore, their work lacks detailed information regarding the testbed configuration and the methodology used to generate the dataset. The authors also restrict their analysis to binary detection, without addressing multi-class detection.

Further, our FL-MU dataset is compared with eleven existing IoT network intrusion datasets in terms of the number of attacks integrated, use of physical and emulated IoT devices, inclusion of IoT protocol-specific attacks, inclusion of IoT network layer attacks, deployment of a Federated Learning approach, size of the dataset, number of instances and features, and attack types. From the overall comparison of FL-MU with existing datasets, as shown in Table 1, the proposed FL-MU outshines the existing ones in terms of the inclusion of a variety of IoT communication protocols and attacks, making it more representative of real-world scenarios. Moreover, we perform an in-depth comparison of existing datasets considering various IoT communication protocols and attack types, depicted in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. From Table 2, it is evident that most existing datasets focus on the MQTT protocol, with only a few including CoAP. Notably, only the MU-IoT dataset covers AMQP and STOMP, while SOAP and DDS remain unexplored in previous works. Moreover, from Table 3, it is observed that none of the eleven datasets includes the recent attacks, viz., Slowite attacks, Selective forwarding attacks, Sybil attacks, and Sinkhole attacks. Therefore, the proposed FL-MU dataset signifies a major contribution to the IoT security research community. This dataset has the potential to support the development and validation of robust and effective security systems for securing IoT networks.

III. FL-MU DATASET GENERATION FRAMEWORK

Our FL-MU dataset is generated from a hybrid IoT testbed that consists of physical and emulated devices. This section describes the details of the components used in developing the FL-MU dataset, including the hardware, IoT communication protocols, software and tools, IoT testbed architecture, attack types, and legitimate as well as attack traffic generation steps for preparing the FL-MU dataset. The detailed description of each component is given next.

A. HARDWARE DEPLOYED

The hardware used to create the FL-MU dataset can be classified into four categories, viz., sensors, single-board computers (SBC), computing devices, and networking devices. The sensors include temperature sensors, humidity sensors, soil moisture sensors, ultrasonic distance sensors, raindrop sensors, dust sensors, webcams, and atmospheric pressure sensors. Moreover, the SBC includes Raspberry Pi5 microprocessors and ESP32 microcontrollers, which enable the publishing of telemetry data to the subscribers inside the FL-MU network testbed. The computing devices include workstations, laptops, and desktops to serve as brokers or

⁷<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11276106>

⁸RPL: Routing Protocol for Low-power and Lossy Networks.

⁹<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964647>

¹⁰<https://manipuruniv.ac.in/CSDmuIoTdataset/>

TABLE 1. Comparison with existing datasets.

Dataset	Year	No. of instances	No. of features	No. of attacks	No. of attacks >10	Physical IoT testbed	Emulated IoT device	IoT protocol based attack	IoT network layer attack	Federated Learning approach
Bot-IoT [11]	2018	73,370,443	43	10	×	×	×	×	×	×
ToN_IoT [12]	2020	22,339,021	44	9	×	✓	✓	×	×	×
Edge-IIoTset [13]	2022	20,952,648	61	14	✓	✓	×	×	×	✓
DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT [14]	2023	3,654,560	30	10	×	✓	×	✓	×	×
FLNET2023 [15]	2023	7,553,724	82	10	×	×	×	×	×	✓
CICIoT2023 [16]	2023	46,686,579	47	33	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
CICIoMT2024 [17]	2024	8,775,013	39	18	✓	✓	×	✓	×	×
UOS_IOTSH_2024 [18]	2024	1,777,880	13	1	×	×	×	×	✓	×
Farm-Flow [19]	2025	1,309,887	101	8	×	✓	×	×	×	×
MU-IoT [9]	2024	34,847,603	121	16	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	✓
NIMS [34]	2025	NA	139	4	×	✓	×	×	×	×
FL-MU (Proposed dataset)	2025	19,057,589	124	11	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

TABLE 2. Protocol-based comparison with existing datasets.

Dataset	MQTT	CoAP	AMQP	STOMP	SOAP	DDS
Bot-IoT [11]	✓	×	×	×	×	×
ToN_IoT [12]	✓	×	×	×	×	×
Edge-IIoTset [13]	✓	×	×	×	×	×
DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT [14]	✓	×	×	×	×	×
FLNET2023 [15]	×	×	×	×	×	×
CICIoT2023 [16]	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
CICIoMT2024 [17]	✓	×	×	×	×	×
UOS_IOTSH_2024 [18]	×	×	×	×	×	×
Farm-Flow [19]	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
MU-IoT [9]	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	×
NIMS [34]	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
FL-MU (Proposed dataset)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

servers, attackers, and subscribers, respectively. Further, the networking devices include routers, switches, and Wireless Access Points, which are used to establish both wired and wireless connections among the devices within the testbed. Additionally, the port mirroring in an L2 switch is utilized for monitoring and capturing the generated network traffic. The descriptions of the sensors and the other devices used in creating the FL-MU dataset are given in Table 4 and Table 5, respectively.

B. IoT PROTOCOLS USED

In this section, a list of IoT communication protocols is discussed. These protocols are basically used in IoT communications at different layers of our IoT network testbed. Additionally, Table 6 provides a summary of the seven protocols, i.e., AMQP, CoAP, DDS, MQTT, SOAP, STOMP, and WebSocket, employed in this testbed.

- *Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP)*: AMQP is a lightweight machine-to-machine messaging protocol that supports many features, such as reliable queuing, flexible routing, transactions, and publish-subscribe [35]. This protocol operates over a broker, e.g., a RabbitMQ broker, which manages the delivery of messages between a publisher (sender) and a subscriber (receiver). Both the publisher and the subscriber exchange messages through a specific topic. AMQP uses TCP as its default transport protocol, providing connection-oriented services, which enhances its reliability. Its reliability, combined with the requirement for small message payloads, makes it particularly suitable for deployment in IoT networks. AMQP is widely adopted in IoT applications because of its reliability and

the ability to persist messages until they are successfully delivered to their destination.

- *Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP)*: CoAP is a lightweight machine-to-machine messaging protocol designed for resource-constrained IoT environments. Unlike AMQP, which supports topic-based messaging, CoAP does not use topic-based communication. Instead, it employs Uniform Resource Identifiers (URI) to enable communication. In this communication, publishers send data to specific URIs representing resources, and subscribers access or observe resources associated with those URIs. When the publishers update the resource (by sending new data to the URI), all subscribed clients (observers) are notified of the updated values. CoAP is particularly suited for IoT environments due to its low bandwidth and power consumption, which are crucial for resource-constrained devices. It operates over User Datagram Protocol (UDP), a connectionless transport protocol, enabling faster communication with minimum overhead. This characteristic is beneficial for IoT devices having limited power that need to transmit small amounts of data with minimal latency.
- *Data Distribution Service (DDS)*: DDS is a middleware protocol and API standard introduced by the Object Management Group (OMG) in 2004 [36]. It provides data-centric connectivity and is widely used in the IoT and Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) because of its high reliability, real-time performance, and data-sharing efficiency. Unlike message-centric protocols like AMQP, MQTT, and STOMP, it uses a publish-subscribe communication method focused on data rather than messages, which makes it ideal for applications requiring real-time data synchronization. Additionally, DDS does not rely on a broker for data routing and uses either UDP or TCP transport layer protocols. It offers different Quality of Services (QoSs) policies, such as communication reliability, fault tolerance, resource consumption, and peer-to-peer communication. Due to its high Quality of Service (QoS) policies, DDS is often preferred for applications in IoT, IIoT, and other distributed systems, particularly in domains such as smart grids, military, healthcare, air-traffic control, and robotics, where real-time data

TABLE 3. Attack-based comparison with existing datasets.

Dataset	MiTM	DoS	DDoS	Slowite DDoS Attack	Selective forwarding Attack	Sybil Attack	Sinkhole Attack
Bot-IoT [11]	×	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
ToN_IoT [12]	✓	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
Edge-IoTset [13]	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	×
DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT [14]	×	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
FLNET2023 [15]	✓	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
CICIoT2023 [16]	✓	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
CICIoMT2024 [17]	×	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
UOS_IOTSH_2024 [18]	×	×	×	×	×	×	✓
Farm-Flow [19]	✓	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
MU-IoT [9]	✓	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
NIMS [34]	×	✓	×	✓	×	×	×
FL-MU(Proposed dataset)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

TABLE 4. Description of Sensors.

Sensor	Model	Communication Protocol	Hardware connected
Temperature Sensor	DHT 22	SOAP	ESP32
Humidity Sensor	DHT 22	CoAP	ESP32
Soil Moisture Sensor	Resistive (HW-080)	STOMP	Raspberry Pi5
Ultrasonic Distance Sensor	HC-SR04	AMQP	Raspberry Pi5
Raindrop Sensor	Resistive (MH-RD Raindrop Sensor Module)	CoAP	Raspberry Pi5
Dust Sensor	GP2Y1010AU0F	MQTT	ESP32
Camera	ESP32 Cam	WebSocket	ESP32
Atmospheric Pressure Sensor	BMP180	MQTT	ESP32

TABLE 5. Description of computing devices, SBC, and networking devices.

Device Type	Equipment	Model	RAM	OS/Firmware
Computing devices	Workstation 0	DELL Precision 7820 Tower	64 GB	Windows 11 Pro
	Workstation 1	DELL Precision 5820 Tower	32 GB	Windows 11 Pro
	Workstation 2	HPZ4G5	64 GB	Windows 11 Pro
	Laptop 0	Lenovo V15	8 GB	Windows 11/Vbox (Kali)
	Laptop 1	Lenovo Ideapad Gaming3	16 GB	Windows 11/Vbox (Kali)
	Laptop 2	Lenovo G50	8 GB	Kali
	Laptop 3	Lenovo Legion 5	16 GB	Windows 11/Vbox (Kali)
	Laptop 4	HP Notebook 13	4 GB	Kali
	Desktop 0-15	Acer All-in-One Veriton Z6694G	8 GB	Windows 11
Server	HPE Proliant DL180Gen10	64 GB	Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS	
Single-board Computers	Raspberry Pi 0	Raspberry Pi5	8GB	Raspberry Pi OS
	Raspberry Pi 1	Raspberry Pi5	4GB	Raspberry Pi OS
	Raspberry Pi 2	Raspberry Pi5	4GB	Raspberry Pi OS
	ESP32 0	ESP-WROOM-32	512 KB	Micropython
	ESP32 1	Node MCU-ESP32	512 KB	Micropython
	ESPCam	ESP32-S	520 KB	Micropython
Networking devices	Router	NetgearRAX40	256 MB	RAX40-V1.0.6.106_1.0.1
	Switch	EnGeniues EWS2910P-FIT	256 MB	EWS2910P-FIT_fw_2.0.08-013
	Wireless Access Point	TP-Link TP-WR845N	32 MB	TL-WR845N(UN)_V4_201214

communication is essential [37]. DDS excels over other protocols in environments that require high reliability, real-time performance, scalability, and data distribution, making it a powerful choice for more complex and mission-critical IoT applications.

- *Message Queuing Telemetry Transport Protocol (MQTT)*: MQTT is a lightweight, bandwidth-efficient, and standardized publish-subscribe protocol introduced by IBM in 1999 [38]. It follows the publish-subscribe model of communication, where a publisher sends messages to a specific topic, and subscribers receive messages by subscribing to that topic. MQTT relies on a central broker not only to route messages between publishers and subscribers but also to manage subscriptions and message delivery. Some well-known

brokers of MQTT include Mosquito, HiveMQ, Really Small Message Broker (RSMB), RabbitMQ, and MQTT.js [38]. Although RabbitMQ is primarily an AMQP broker, it can support MQTT through plugins. MQTT offers three levels of QoS, i.e., QoS0, QoS1, and QoS2. In QoS0, there is no guarantee of delivering the message, while QoS1 guarantees delivery of the message at least once, and QoS2 ensures delivery of the message exactly once, which is achieved by the use of a 4-step handshaking approach.

- *Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP)*: SOAP is an XML-based lightweight protocol used in distributed environments for message exchange. A SOAP message consists of three elements, i.e., Envelope, Header, and Body [39]. The envelope is used to verify whether

TABLE 6. Description of protocols used.

IoT Application Protocols	Transport Protocols	Description	Uses
Advanced Message Queuing Protocol	TCP/IP	It is a lightweight protocol that supports high reliability and guaranteed message delivery. It supports asynchronous communication with publish/subscribe interface.	It is mostly used in financial IoT applications, and large scale IoT network which requires high reliability.
Constrained Application Protocol	UDP	It is a lightweight and low power consumption protocol, highly efficient for constrained devices with low memory.	It is mostly used in smart home devices, wearable health monitoring systems, smart agriculture and smart cities.
Data Distribution Service	TCP, RTPS/ UDP	It provides real-time, low latency communication. It is highly reliable and supports fault tolerance.	Used in Internet of Drones that requires low latency in data exchange.
Message Queuing Telemetry Transport Protocol	TCP/IP	It provides lightweight with low overhead communication, low bandwidth consumption, reliable delivery with multiple Quality of Service levels. It does not restrict to one-to-one communication.	Used in smart homes, smart sensors and wearables.
Simple Object Access Protocol	HTTP, SMTP	It provides highly standardized communication. It also supports WS-security rendering secured and reliable services.	Used in sensitive IoT applications like healthcare.
Simple (or Streaming) Text Oriented Messaging Protocol	TCP/IP	It is a simple, lightweight and text based protocol. Messaging in human-readable form.	Used in real-time messaging applications like smart smoke detector, and soil moisture level detector.
WebSocket	TCP	It is a full-duplex protocol.	Used in real-time smart surveillance camera, smart home devices, and environmental sensors.

the document is in SOAP format or not. The header contains the authentication data, and the body contains the XML format data. Although it is relatively heavier than MQTT, CoAP, and AMQP, and not suitable for resource-constrained IoT devices, it is used in IoT applications where reliability and secure message exchange are critical. It ensures reliable communication by leveraging Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) or Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP), while it ensures secure message transmission by using WS-Security and WS-ReliableMessaging, which guarantees delivery of messages even in the case of network issues. Hence, SOAP is beneficial for IoT environments where security and data loss are critical.

- *Simple Streaming Text Oriented Messaging Protocol (STOMP)*: STOMP is a lightweight, text-based messaging protocol used in distributed systems for communication between message brokers and clients. It is designed to work with message-oriented middleware over protocols like HTTP and TCP. It supports the publish-subscribe approach, making it applicable for real-time communication in distributed systems. Unlike the complex protocols that rely on a comprehensive API, STOMP uses simple message operations with acknowledgements, making it easier to implement and more flexible for various use cases [37].
- *WebSocket*: It is a bidirectional communication protocol that allows continuous, simultaneous data exchange over a single persistent TCP connection. In IoT camera systems, it enables real-time communication between the device and a remote server with minimum overhead. WebSocket maintains an open connection and uses

a lightweight 2-byte message header, reducing the need for repeated handshakes. While it lacks built-in reliability mechanisms and may not be optimal for highly constrained devices, it can be secured using TLS/SSL and provides an efficient transport layer for time-sensitive IoT camera applications [40].

C. SOFTWARE AND TOOLS DEPLOYED

The testbed used for creating the FL-MU dataset executes different tools and systems. We install various software, viz., RabbitMQ, Dnsmasq, Python, Micropython, Visual Studio Code, MPY-Jama, Winscap, and FastDDS. Moreover, we utilize tools such as Ettercap, Hping3, and BoNeSi to launch various attacks, while TCPDUMP is used to capture the network traffic through port mirroring, as described in Table 7. To implement the MQTT protocol, the RabbitMQ and paho-mqtt clients are used. To enable the CoAP protocol, we use asyncio, aiocoap, and gpiozero Python libraries. Meanwhile, the Pika Python library is used to implement the AMQP protocol. Stomp and psutil Python libraries are also used to implement the STOMP protocol. The spyne Python library was also used to implement the SOAP protocol. Moreover, to implement the DDS protocol, we use FastDDS, an open-source software in our testbed.

D. IoT TESTBED SETUP

We set up a hybrid testbed consisting of both physical and emulated devices at the Manipur University cybersecurity lab to generate a realistic IoT network intrusion dataset. The dataset includes both legitimate and attack traffic generated from various protocol-specific IoT communication systems.

TABLE 7. Description of software and tools deployed.

Software/Tool	Application
RabbitMQ	Broker for MQTT, AMQP, and STOMP protocols
FastDDS	DDS (Data Distribution Service) protocol implementation
Visual studio code	Python code editor
MPY-Jama	Micropython library that provides lightweight python interface for ESP32
WinSCP	To manage files remotely
Ettercap	This tool is used to conduct man-in-the-middle attack
Dnsmasq	It is used to conduct Sinkhole attack
Hping3	To simulate DoS and DDoS attack
BoNeSi	To launch DDoS attack
TCPDUMP	To capture the network traffic in the LAN
Python	Programming language used
Micropython	Programming language used for embedded devices such as ESP32

Our testbed consists of three distributed clients and a central server, as shown in Figure 1. Each of the three clients is considered to possess an identical network setup. A representative framework of the network structure of each federated client (FL client) is shown in Figure 2. This network framework consists of various IoT services, senders, receivers, attackers, and victims. In addition, we set up the necessary network equipment, mentioned in Section III-A, to enable network connectivity among the workstations, desktops, laptops, and a server. Here, the router, L2 switch, access point, workstations, desktops, and server are interconnected through Ethernet cables. Moreover, the IoT devices and laptops are connected through the Wireless Access Point. Further, the IoT devices served either as senders, brokers, or servers. The workstations functioned as brokers, storage points, and computing nodes. Laptops are used as attackers, while desktops act as bots. An L2 switch is used for port mirroring and capturing the generated traffic locally in each FL client.

In this setup, we use three Raspberry Pi5 microprocessors, four ESP32 microcontrollers, and different sensors as IoT devices that are listed in Table 4. In each FL client, we employ two Kali Linux systems to launch attacks and generate malicious network behaviour over the client's network. The connected IoT devices communicate with other entities of the network using IoT communication protocols as explained in Section III-B. The protocols like MQTT, AMQP, and STOMP work in a publish-subscribe mode with an intermediate broker. In our setup, we use the RabbitMQ broker to support these three protocols. The IoT devices included in the FL client 1 are one Raspberry Pi5 and two ESP32 microcontrollers, connecting the soil moisture sensor, temperature sensor, and web camera. These devices communicate with the other devices using STOMP, SOAP, and WebSocket protocols. Similarly, the IoT devices included in the FL client 2 are two ESP32 microcontrollers embedding the raindrop sensor and humidity sensor, and an emulated IoT device, communicating to other devices over the CoAP and DDS protocols, respectively. Likewise, the IoT devices included in the FL client 3 are one

Raspberry Pi5 and two ESP32 microcontrollers embedding the ultrasonic sound sensor, dust sensor, and atmospheric pressure sensor, respectively, communicating over AMQP and MQTT protocols.

E. OVERVIEW OF IoT NETWORK ATTACKS

In the FL-MU dataset, we consider different types of attacks generated from the network and application layers of an IoT network. A detailed description of different attack types is highlighted here. The FL-MU dataset includes six types of attacks, i.e., DoS, DDoS, MiTM, Sinkhole attack, Sybil attack, and Selective forwarding attack, which are further categorized into a total of 11 attack classes, i.e., TCP_SYN_FLOOD, ARP_Poisoning, Sybil Attack, Sinkhole Attack, Slowite, MQTT_CONNECT_FLOOD, AMQP_FLOOD, DNS_AMPLIFICATION, STOMP_FLOOD, SOAP_FLOOD, and Selective forwarding attack. A brief description of these attacks is given below.

- 1) *Denial of Service attack (DoS) attack*: In this attack, an attacker aims to exhaust the resources of a server or target, making it unavailable to legitimate users [41]. TCP-SYN Flooding attack is one such type of DoS attack that exploits the TCP handshake process to overwhelm and disrupt a target server. Here, the attacker sends multiple SYN packets to the server, and the server then responds with SYN-ACK packets. However, the attacker intentionally never responds to the final ACK packet, leaving the server with multiple half-open connections, consuming its resources and causing it to become unresponsive to legitimate users.
- 2) *Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks*: DDoS attacks typically begin with network scanning to gather vulnerable devices. Once a vulnerable device is found, the attacker inserts malicious code into the device through the exposed point and compromises the device. These compromised devices, known as zombies or bots, are then controlled by the attacker to form a botnet. Then the botnet is used to launch a coordinated attack on the target, often in the form of a distributed nature [42]. Among the various types of DoS/DDoS attacks, we focus on seven specific types, as highlighted below.

- *MQTT connect flooding attack*: It is a type of DoS/DDoS attack where the attacker overwhelms the MQTT broker by flooding with a large volume of CONNECT requests, eventually making it unavailable to legitimate nodes or clients.
- *Slowite attack*: [43] In this attack, the attacker keeps the connection to the MQTT broker open for a long duration by sending partial and slow requests. This eventually prevents the broker from managing connections and exhausting its resources. Unlike other DoS/DDoS attacks, the Slowite attack relies on slow, low-bandwidth connections to exhaust the broker resources. Thus

FIGURE 1. Conceptual FL-MU testbed architecture from FL perspective.

FIGURE 2. Overview of LAN setup for an FL client.

making it impossible for new legitimate nodes to connect to the broker [44].

- *AMQP flooding attack*: This DoS/DDoS attack aims to overwhelm the AMQP broker by sending a large number of connection requests, causing the broker to be unable to handle legitimate service requests.
 - *DNS amplification attack*: This is a type of DoS/DDoS attack where the attacker exploits open DNS servers to overwhelm the target server with a huge amount of traffic. The attacker sends DNS queries with a spoofed IP address, i.e., the target's IP address, so that the DNS server responds with large responses to the target [9]. As the DNS server sends responses to the target, the volume of traffic increases significantly, leading to resource exhaustion and service disruption for the target system.
 - *SOAP flooding attack*: This is a DoS/DDoS attack targeting the systems that rely on SOAP communication protocol, particularly in web service environments. Here, the attacker sends multiple SOAP requests to the server to exhaust its resources and cause denial of service.
 - *STOMP flooding attack*: This is a type of DoS/DDoS attack targeting the STOMP messaging system. In this attack, the attacker floods the STOMP broker with a large number of connection requests or STOMP messages, overwhelming the broker and consuming its resources. This causes service disruptions or denial of service for legitimate users.
- 3) *Man-in-the-middle (MiTM) attack*: In this attack, an attacker intercepts communication between two entities to either manipulate or steal the sensitive data exchanged. The attacker lies between two target systems. A MiTM attack enables an attacker or malicious agent to intercept, transmit, or receive information for another party without the knowledge of either party [45]. The aim of this attack is to conduct eavesdropping, steal information, and manipulate data. During eavesdropping, the attacker may forward the data between the parties, making the exchange appear legitimate while secretly intercepting, altering, or injecting malicious content. The most common communication channels where MiTM can be conducted include Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, Universal Mobile Telecommunications System (UMTS), Radio Frequency, Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM), and Near-field Communication (NFC) [45]. Spoofing is the initial step to perform the MiTM attacks, where an attacker impersonates one of the parties involved in the communication between two parties. This is typically achieved using Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) spoofing. Other spoofing techniques, such as IP spoofing, DNS spoofing, and DHCP spoofing, are also commonly employed in MiTM attacks.
- 4) *Selective forwarding attack*: In this attack, an attacker compromises a node within the network and gains access to its authentication and encryption details [46]. The compromised node, under the attacker's control, is used to carry out the attack. Since the attack is launched from within the network, it becomes challenging to defend. Additionally, this attack can result from a MiTM attack, where the attacker intercepts communication to manipulate the transmitted data. The attacker selectively forwards only certain portions of the data, making the communication flow appear normal, or drops them entirely. This disruption can lead to both data manipulation and loss. The impact of this attack is especially severe in the realm of IoT, where accurate data is essential for the proper functioning of systems like smart healthcare and IoT home security devices [47].
- 5) *Sinkhole attack*: It is an attack where the communication between nodes and the sink is disrupted by making the attacker's node appear as the sink, thus blocking or redirecting the traffic to the attacker's sink [48]. This attack is easily launched in IoT networks, opting for wireless sensor networks (WSN) where the hop-by-hop routing mechanism is deployed [49]. However, it is often challenging to defend against it [50]. As in WSN, the sink plays a critical role in communication between the nodes. The attacker's sink pretends to have a lower hop count of 0 to appear as the actual sink, to make nearby nodes believe that they have found a shorter path to route their data to the sink. Hence, all the data will pass through the attacker sink, thus allowing the attacker to intercept and block the actual communication to its destination [50].
- 6) *Sybil attack*: [51] In this attack, the malicious node or the attacker spoofs its identity or creates multiple fake identities to send false information in the IoT network. This attack leads to hazardous results in the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) and other critical IoT applications [52].

F. TRAFFIC GENERATION

The traffic generated in our testbed is categorized into two types, i.e., legitimate traffic and attack traffic. To ensure that the network traffic consists solely of the generated legitimate and attack traffic from the testbed, the testbed was completely isolated from the Internet. This isolation guarantees a controlled environment and eliminates interference from external networks.

1) LEGITIMATE TRAFFIC GENERATION

To generate legitimate traffic, we consider three FL clients, and each client network is depicted as shown in Figure 2. Although a simple smartphone can represent a client of an FL network, we have shown a complete network structure

having multiple IoT devices as well as non-IoT devices for generating a huge amount of network traffic incorporating 11 types of network attack patterns. Each FL client consists of two main components, i.e., senders and receivers. The senders are those IoT devices that capture and send environmental data such as temperature, humidity, soil moisture, rainfall, atmospheric pressure, sound, real-time video streams, and dust levels. While the receivers are those devices in the network receiving the telemetry data from the senders, such as Raspberry Pi5 and Workstations. The network traffic generated from communication among these devices is considered legitimate. Moreover, each FL client's network is isolated by disconnecting from the Internet to ensure that no other malicious activities are running in the background. This is further achieved by examining the network using the tool Wireshark.¹¹ Additionally, the communications between the senders and the receivers are carried out using different IoT communication protocols described in Section III-C.

A complete conceptual framework of the FL clients' network is shown in Figure 1. The Client 1 comprises an edge computing node, i.e., the workstation, and IoT devices such as soil moisture sensing devices, temperature and humidity sensing devices, and a real-time video capturing webcam. The workstation serves both as a broker and an edge computing node. Communication between this edge computing node and the IoT devices is done using STOMP, SOAP, and WebSocket protocols, respectively. The Client 2 comprises a rainfall sensing device, dust level sensing devices, and an emulated IoT device that communicates with the Raspberry Pi5 (edge computing node) over CoAP and DDS protocols. Here, the Raspberry Pi5 serves both as the CoAP server and the edge computing node. The Client 3 comprises an edge computing node, i.e., the workstation, and IoT devices such as ultrasonic sound sensing devices, rainfall sensing devices, and dust level sensing devices. Similar to the above FL clients, the workstation serves both as the broker and the edge computing node. Communication between the edge computing node and the IoT devices is carried out using AMQP and MQTT protocols.

The IoT devices in each FL client capture the environmental data from their surroundings and send it to their respective computing nodes over the specified protocols, as presented in Table 4. During the process of sending and receiving the telemetry data, legitimate network traffic is generated within the network of each FL client. The generated legitimate network traffic is captured using port mirroring and stored in each FL client.

2) ATTACK TRAFFIC GENERATION

To generate the attack traffic, we consider the following threat model. The model considers an IoT network comprising several IoT devices, servers, computing nodes, and end users. The adversaries are assumed to be internal nodes, i.e., the compromised Kali systems, and desktops forming a distributed botnet with partial knowledge of the local

topology and protocol behavior within the network. The primary goals of the attackers are to disrupt services, intercept communications, drop packets, and manipulate routing information using tools such as Hping3, Ettercap, Dnsmasq, and BoNeSi to mount DoS/DDoS, MiTM, Sinkhole, Sybil, and Selective forwarding attacks. The dataset reflects typical attack scenarios, including DoS and DDoS attacks that exhaust network resources, MiTM attacks that intercept communications, Sinkhole attacks that mislead routing by attracting and dropping traffic, Sybil attacks that use multiple fake identities to influence routing and trust mechanisms, and Selective forwarding attacks that drop specific packets to degrade reliability. The severity of impact varies according to the attack launched. MiTM, Sinkhole, and Selective forwarding attacks pose a high severity to the confidentiality and integrity of the data exchange among the various servers and IoT devices. While DoS, DDoS, and Sybil attacks cause high availability impact on the service and resource of the target, i.e., the servers in our network. Additionally, the Slowite attack causes medium severity as they are hard to detect but degrade the resource availability, disrupting the communication between the MQTT server and the users. This model provides a general representation of adversarial behavior in IoT networks for evaluating intrusion detection and defense strategies from a resource-constrained environment.

Considering the above threat model, the attack traffic is generated by launching six IoT communication-based attacks in our own testbed, as described in Section III-E. To launch the attacks within the network of each FL client, we use two Kali systems as attackers. The DoS attack is launched within the network of Client 2 and Client 3, while DDoS attacks are launched within the network of all the clients. However, MiTM and Sinkhole attacks are launched within the network of Client 1. The Selective forwarding and the Sybil attacks are launched within the network of Client 2 and Client 3, respectively. Next, we discuss the execution of these attacks, whose behaviors are incorporated into our FL-MU dataset.

a: DENIAL-OF-SERVICE (DoS) ATTACK

The Kali systems perform Transmission Control Protocol Synchronize Flood (TCP_SYN_FLOOD) to conduct the DoS attack. Here, the attacker sends multiple TCP synchronization packets to the victims, i.e., the CoAP server of Client 2 and the MQTT broker of Client 3, using the Hping3 tool. This attack exhausts the server's resources and causes it to lose connection with the legitimate users. Each FL client captures the traffic generated during this attack using the TCPDUMP tool. The physical configuration detail of this attack is shown in Table 8.

b: DISTRIBUTED DENIAL-OF-SERVICE (DDoS) ATTACKS

A conceptual diagram of the DDoS attacks is shown in Figure 3. The attack is performed using a Windows workstation as the attacker. Initially, we perform a quick scan of the network using the Nmap tool to find and

¹¹A network monitoring tool.

TABLE 8. Description of denial of service attack scenario.

Attack Type	Attacker	Victim IP Address	DoS Type	Traffic Capturing Point	Attack Tool Used	Impact
Denial of Service Attack	Kali (192.168.1.23)	CoAP Server 192.168.1.2	TCP_SYN_FLOOD	Switch	Hping3	Gradually the communication between the server and the legitimate nodes was completely severed, and the server was unable to respond to legitimate requests.
		MQTT Broker 192.168.1.50				

compromise vulnerable devices to create a botnet. We are able to create twenty bots, communicating with the bot controller over the AMQP protocol, to conduct the DDoS attacks. The IP addresses of the controller, victims, types of DDoS, traffic capturing point, and the tool used are given in Table 9. The victims of the DDoS attacks depend on the type of flooding attacks employed. The STOMP_FLOOD and SOAP_FLOOD attacks are launched on Client 1, targeting the RabbitMQ broker and the SOAP server, respectively. Similarly, the MQTT-oriented DDoS attacks, i.e., Slowite, MQTT_CONNECT_FLOOD, and AMQP_FLOOD attacks, are launched on Client 2 and Client 3, targeting the brokers. Furthermore, the DNS_AMPLIFICATION attack is launched on Client 2, targeting the CoAP server. The victims of these attacks eventually become unable to provide service to their legitimate users. These attacks overwhelm the network by consuming available bandwidth and exhausting system resources, rendering services inaccessible to genuine users. The mitigation of such an attack can be achieved by the deployment of an IDS, which monitors network traffic for abnormal patterns. When excessive network traffic is detected from multiple sources, the IDS alerts the network controller either block the incoming traffic or redirect it away from its intended target. However, traffic generated from the Slowite attack is more challenging to mitigate. This attack sends data at a very slow rate to keep server connections open, resembling the behaviour of a legitimate user. As their traffic generated resembles that of legitimate network traffic, it is often difficult for detection systems. The traffic generated during these activities is captured in the Ubuntu server by mirroring the ports of the targets' systems using the TCPDUMP tool. Each FL client performs this capturing process within its own network.

c: MAN-IN-THE-MIDDLE (MiTM) ATTACK

This attack is launched on our testbed using the Ettercap tool executed on Kali Linux systems. We initiate this attack by performing ARP poisoning to intercept the communication between the broker and publishers, as well as between the publishers and the servers. Basically, this attack targets two groups of victims, i.e., the group that is sending the data and the other group that is receiving the data. In our case, the IoT devices that send the perceived sensor data to their subscribers constitute the victim 1 group, and the other systems or devices in our lab receiving the data constitute the victim 2 group. The traffic generated during this communication is captured in the Ubuntu server by mirroring the ports of the victims. Figure 4 represents the complete scenario of the MiTM attack. The

description of the devices used in this attack is shown in Table 10.

d: SELECTIVE FORWARDING ATTACK

To conduct the Selective forwarding attack, as shown in Figure 5, we employ an emulated IoT device that publishes the temperature data, a victim subscriber, and the attacker. This attack is executed on the communication of IoT devices running over the DDS protocol. The attacker places itself between the publisher and the subscriber to intercept the published data. Further, using the attacker device, we manipulate the publisher's generated data by dropping 50% of the received data before forwarding it to the subscriber. This attack undermines the integrity of the published data by manipulating it during transmission. As a result, the subscriber receives the altered data, unaware that it has been tampered with during transit. Similarly, the generated traffic is captured and stored in an Ubuntu server.

e: SINKHOLE ATTACK

This attack is launched using a Kali system. The attack is initiated by configuring a Sinkhole in the Kali system, using the Dnsmasq software. This attack compromises the router and updates the routing information. This manipulation causes legitimate network traffic, specifically, the publish-subscribe communications, to be redirected to the sinkhole created, ultimately dropping the packets. This prevents legitimate traffic from reaching its intended destination. The generated traffic is captured and stored in the Ubuntu server. The description of the attacker, victim, and tools is shown in Table 11.

f: SYBIL ATTACK

Among the three variants of the Sybil attacks, we perform the Sybil Attack-1 (Type-A Sybil attack). Here, using a malicious node (desktop), we create multiple fake nodes. These multiple fake nodes simultaneously send requests to the RabbitMQ broker for sensor-generated data. This way, the broker is overwhelmed with multiple requests, and it can no longer respond to the requests coming from the legitimate nodes. The details of the nodes participating in this attack are shown in Table 12.

G. CAPTURED NETWORK TRAFFIC IN EACH FL CLIENTS

As described in Section III, our FL-based IoT network testbed consists of three FL clients, each operating within its own network. The network traffic collected by each FL client remains local and is not shared centrally. Due to

TABLE 9. Description of distributed denial of service attack scenario.

Attack Type	Bot Controller	Target	DDoS type	Traffic Capturing Point	Attack Tool	Impact
Distributed Denial of Service	192.168.1.52	CoAP Server (192.168.1.2) RabbitMQ Broker (192.168.1.50) RabbitMQ Broker (192.168.1.51)	Slowite, MQTT_CONNECT_FLOOD, AMQP_FLOOD, SOAP_FLOOD, STOMP_FLOOD, and DNS_AMPLIFICATION	Switch	Hping3, BoNeSi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The server's resources were exhausted, causing it to immediately lose communication with legitimate nodes. Attack source identification is challenging due to traffic from multiple nodes.

FIGURE 3. Diagrammatic presentation of Distributed Denial of Service Attack.

FIGURE 4. Diagrammatic presentation of Man-in-the-middle Attack.

differences in IoT device types and communication protocols, the datasets generated are also heterogeneous, particularly in terms of attack types and characteristics. The traffic

captured on Client 1's network includes legitimate and attack traffic of SOAP flooding, STOMP flooding, MiTM, and Sinkhole attacks. While the traffic captured on Client

TABLE 10. Description of man-in-the-middle attack scenario.

Attack Type	Target 1		Attacker	Target 2		Traffic Capturing Point	Attack Tool Used	Impact
	Device	IP Address		Device	IP Address			
Man-in-the-Middle Attack	Esp32 1	192.168.1.71	Kali 192.168.1.23	Workstation 0	192.168.1.50	Switch	Ettercap	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Integrity of data is compromised. ● The attacker gains access to the transmitted data without the knowledge of either the sender or the receiver.
	Esp32 0	192.168.1.70		Workstation 1	192.168.1.51			
	Raspberry pi5 1	192.168.1.4		Workstation 1	192.168.1.51			
	Raspberry pi5 2	192.168.1.6		Workstation 0	192.168.1.50			
	Raspberry pi5 0	192.168.1.2		Lenovo Laptop	192.168.1.16			
	Workstation 2 Ubuntu OS	192.168.1.18		Workstation 2 Ubuntu OS	192.168.1.21			
	ESP32 cam	192.168.1.73		Workstation 2 Laptops	192.168.1.52			
					192.168.1.9			
			192.168.1.7					

FIGURE 5. Diagrammatic presentation of selective forwarding attack.

TABLE 11. Description of sinkhole attack scenario.

Attack Type	Attacker	Victim IP address	Traffic Capturing Point	Software Used	Impact
Sinkhole Attack	Kali (192.168.1.10)	192.168.1.2	Switch	Dnsmasq	Redirects all the traffic to the malicious DNS server.
		192.168.1.4			
		192.168.1.6			
		192.168.1.8			
		192.168.1.15			
		192.168.1.16			
		192.168.1.17			
		192.168.1.20			
		192.168.1.21			
		192.168.1.50			
		192.168.1.51			
		192.168.1.52			
		192.168.1.73			

2's network includes legitimate and attack traffic of DNS amplification, MQTT connect flooding, TCP SYN flooding, and Selective forwarding attacks. Moreover, the traffic captured on Client 3's network includes legitimate and attack

traffic of AMQP flooding, Slowite, TCP SYN flooding, and Sybil attacks. The captured network traffic of each FL client undergoes feature extraction to obtain a dataset for each client separately.

TABLE 12. Description of Sybil attack scenario.

Attack Type	Attacker	Victim IP address	Traffic Capturing Point	Impact
Sybil Attack	192.168.1.5	MQTT Broker (192.168.1.50)	Switch	Leads to denial of service for legitimate nodes.
	192.168.1.11			
	192.168.1.12			
	192.168.1.14			
	192.168.1.19			
	192.168.1.20			
	192.168.1.22			
	192.168.1.24			
	192.168.1.25	STOMP Broker (192.168.1.51)		
	192.168.1.26			
	192.168.1.27			
	192.168.1.28			
	192.168.1.29			
	192.168.1.31			
	192.168.1.32			
	192.168.1.33			
192.168.1.34				
192.168.1.35				
192.168.1.36				

Algorithm 1 : Feature Extraction and Labeling

Require: Network traffic types $TT = \{tt_1, tt_2, \dots, tt_n\}$, which are generated in different Timestamps $TS = \{ts_1, ts_2, \dots, ts_n\}$, where n is the number of traffic types and $n > 1$.

Ensure: Extracted traffic features with labels, $ETL = \{tt_1.csv, tt_2.csv, \dots, tt_n.csv, \}$

- 1: **for** $tt_i \in TT$ & $ts_i \in TS$, where $1 < i \leq n$, **do**
- 2: $RCT \leftarrow Generate\&Capture(tt_i, ts_i)$ # tt_i network traffic type is generated using the respective application or tool at timestamp ts_i .
- 3: $ET \leftarrow ExtractFeatures(RCT)$ # The flow features ET are extracted from the Raw Captured Traffic (RCT) using the module $ExtractFeatures()$.
- 4: $ET['type'] \leftarrow tt_i$
- 5: $ET['category'] \leftarrow Category[tt_i]$
- 6: $ET['label'] \leftarrow Label[tt_i]$
- 7: $ETL \leftarrow Save(ET, tt_i.csv)$
- 8: **end for**
- 9: **return** ETL

As shown in Algorithm 1, during the creation of our FL-MU dataset, we generate and capture various network traffic types, i.e., $TT = \{tt_1, tt_2, \dots, tt_n\}$, as given in Section III-F, in respective timestamps, i.e., $TS = \{ts_1, ts_2, \dots, ts_n\}$, where $n > 1$, on our own network testbed. Using the $Generate\&Capture()$ module, the raw network traffic (RCT) of each traffic type $tt_i \in TT$ is generated and captured in its corresponding timestamp $ts_i \in TS$. The $Generate\&Capture()$ module utilizes respective applications or tools to generate each $tt_i \in TT$ and capture the generated network traffic using the tool ‘TCPDUMP’.

The network traffic generation and capturing are performed in a closed network environment within our own testbed, ensuring traffic cannot flow from our testbed to the global network or vice versa. Then, using the $ExtractFeatures()$ module, 121 flow-based features (ET)

are extracted from the RCT . This extraction is carried out using the technique outlined in the work [9]. Since we generate and capture each network traffic $tt_i \in TT$ at its respective timestamp ts_i using the corresponding applications or tools, we can precisely assign class labels to the extracted flow-based features ET . For example, at a particular timestamp ts_i , using the attacking tool ‘BoNeSi’, we launched the AMQP flooding attack, and captured the associated network traffic. Therefore, we assigned the value of class label ‘type’ as ‘AMQP_FLOOD’ for extracted flow-based features ET against the captured raw network traffic of AMQP flooding attack. Moreover, as the AMQP flooding attack was launched using the tool ‘BoNeSi’ with multiple spoofed IP addresses, the attack is categorized as a DDoS attack. Therefore, the value of the class label ‘category’ of ET for the AMQP flooding attack is assigned as ‘DDoS’. Likewise, since the AMQP flooding attack is launched using the attacking tool ‘BoNeSi’, the generated network traffic is attack traffic. Therefore, the value of the class label ‘label’ of the ET for the AMQP flooding attack is assigned as ‘attack’. In this way, we can precisely assign the class labels of the ET for each captured raw network traffic.

The class label ‘label’ distribution in the dataset of the three clients is presented in Figures 6, 9, and 12, respectively. Similarly, the distribution of the class label ‘category’ for the three clients is illustrated in Figures 7, 10, and 13, respectively. The distribution of the class label ‘type’ for each client is presented in Figures 8, 11, and 14, respectively. Moreover, to assess feature relevance with respect to the target classes, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) is computed across the complete feature set. Based on the resulting correlation scores, the top ten relevant features are selected for each client. Subsequently, correlation heatmaps are generated considering the top ten features along with the corresponding class labels. The heatmaps of the feature-class correlation for the three clients are shown in Figures 15, 16, and 17, respectively.

FIGURE 6. Label class distribution of Client 1 dataset.

FIGURE 10. Category class distribution of Client 2 dataset.

FIGURE 7. Category class distribution of Client 1 dataset.

FIGURE 11. Type class distribution of Client 2 dataset.

FIGURE 8. Type class distribution of Client 1 dataset.

FIGURE 12. Label class distribution of Client 3 dataset.

FIGURE 9. Label class distribution of Client 2 dataset.

H. FINAL FL-MU DATASET

The final FL-MU dataset contains four distinct sets of data, i.e., the raw network traffic captured in pcap format, the

extracted individual CSV files for each legitimate and attack scenarios of the FL clients, a combined CSV file for each FL client, and the final merged dataset named FL_MU in CSV format. The merged FL_MU.csv dataset comprises more than 19 million instances, out of which more than 1 million instances belong to the legitimate class, and the remaining 18,054,798 instances correspond to six categories of attacks as shown in Table 13.

The overall size of our FL-MU dataset is 8.56 GB. The FL-MU dataset is relatively smaller in size compared to

FIGURE 13. Category class distribution of Client 3 dataset.

FIGURE 14. Type class distribution of Client 3 dataset.

FIGURE 15. Feature-class correlation of Client 1 dataset.

well-known IoT network intrusion datasets, such as Bot-IoT (16.7 GB). This difference arises because FL-MU specifically focuses on IoT network-generated traffic, excluding traditional traffic from non-IoT-related communications. Also, due to resource constraints, we consider only three FL clients in generating the dataset. The dataset is scalable to the number

FIGURE 16. Feature-Class correlation of Client 2 dataset.

FIGURE 17. Feature-class correlation of Client 3 dataset.

of clients and other resources. By increasing the number of clients, more IoT network traffic can be generated from our testbed. However, the inclusion of network traffic of various IoT network layer-based attacks makes the FL-MU dataset comprehensive, reflecting real-world IoT cyber threats. This makes the FL-MU dataset a valuable resource for researchers aiming to develop more accurate and robust IoT network security systems.

Additionally, the FL-MU dataset is generated from a very generic and simple IoT network testbed consisting of only three clients, seven IoT protocols, thirty IoT devices, and eleven attack types. However, our testbed is developed as an extensible architecture, enabling researchers to adapt it for specific applications. This flexibility allows the dataset to be expanded by integrating a wider range of IoT devices, protocols, and evolving attack types. Moreover, the number of clients can be increased by connecting

to additional FL client networks. By scaling up clients, protocols, devices, and attack types, the generalizability of the FL-MU dataset can be significantly improved, as the dataset contains advanced network attack types and other features. So, any IDS can be developed and validated using our FL-MU dataset. This would help in generalizing the dataset for the development and evaluation of different types of IDS. Our testbed also supports adaptation to large-scale industrial applications with a focus on industrial IoT clients, considering industrial IoT protocols, devices, and attack scenarios. Hence, the dataset and related implementation codes are made publicly available at the Kaggle repository: <https://doi.org/10.34740/kaggle/dsv/13106381>, for additional benchmarking with an extra scale of each component.

I. STRUCTURE OF FL-MU DATASET REPOSITORY

The repository structure of our FL-MU dataset is shown in Figure 18. The repository consists of a directory named FL-MU dataset. It has four sub-directories, as follows:

- 1) *PCAP directory*: This directory further contains two sub-directories, Attack and Normal. The Attack sub-directories hold the raw pcap files for all attack types included in the FL-MU dataset, with separate sub-directories for each attack category, i.e., DDoS, DoS, MiTM, Selective forwarding Attack, Sinkhole Attack, and Sybil Attack. The legitimate sub-directories contain two raw pcap files representing legitimate network traffic. The DDoS subdirectories contain seven files, namely, AMQP flooding attack file, two DNS amplification attack files, MQTT connect flooding attack file, Slowite attack file, SOAP flooding attack file, and STOMP flooding attack file. The DoS sub-directory contains the TCP synchronization flooding attack file, the MiTM sub-directory consists of two ARP poisoning attack files captured at two different timings, the Selective forwarding attack sub-directory consists of the Selective forwarding attack file, and the Sybil attack sub-directory consists of the Sybil attack file.
- 2) *CSV directory*: This directory stores the data converted from pcap format to CSV format after feature extraction only, without data preprocessing. Similar to the PCAP directory, it is organized into two sub-directories: Attack and Normal. The Attack sub-directory contains the CSV files for the different attack types, such as DDoS, DoS, MiTM, Selective forwarding, Sinkhole, and Sybil attacks, while the legitimate sub-directory holds the CSV files for legitimate traffic data.
- 3) *Python_Codes directory*: This directory contains four Jupyter notebook files, providing programs for validating the existing FL-based IoT network IDSs on our FL-MU dataset.

- 4) *Final Dataset directory*: This directory contains the final FL-MU dataset, which consists of the individual FL client's datasets (viz., C1_data.csv, C2_data.csv, and C3_data.csv) and the FL_MU.csv (a merged version of the three client datasets). The datasets in this directory are provided in their raw form, with no additional preprocessing such as sampling, encoding, or removal of features.

TABLE 13. Instances of each class in the FL_MU dataset.

Class	Category	Type	No. of Instances
Attack	Selective forwarding attack	Selective forwarding	17,259
		AMQP flooding	231,230
	DDoS instances	DNS amplification	1,947
		MQTT connect flood	70,703
		Slowite	61,155
		SOAP flooding	505
		STOMP flooding	2,804
		DoS instances	TCP SYN Flood
	MiTM attack instances	ARP poisoning	494,815
	Sinkhole attack instances	DNS sinkhole	307,212
Sybil attack instances	Sybil	443,440	
Legitimate	Legitimate	Legitimate	1,002,791
Total instances in FL-MU			19,057,589

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The objective of this experiment is to evaluate the performance of state-of-the-art FL-based IDSs in identifying vulnerabilities of IoT networks using our FL-MU dataset. FL models are trained and tested on each client's local data ('C1_data.csv', 'C2_data.csv', and 'C3_data.csv'), without applying the final merged 'FL_MU.csv' dataset. The performance of each FL model is evaluated on binary and multiclass detection tasks, considering only the local data of a client. The models are implemented on Jupyter Notebook IDE using Python libraries such as Numpy, Keras, Scikit-learn, and Pandas. Moreover, the performance of the models is evaluated using Accuracy (ACY), Precision (PRN), Recall (RCL), F1_Score (f1), Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) metrics, and Attack Success Rate (ASR), as described in Section IV-B. The experiment is conducted on a Windows 11 Pro workstation with 64 GB RAM. An exploratory data analysis is performed on the FL-MU dataset, as discussed in section IV-A. For this experiment, we pick up five FL-based state-of-the-art IDSs, viz., CNN-GRU, PCC_CNN, and FELIDS, which consist of three different DL-based methods, viz., CNN, DNN, and RNN. The description of these five models are provided below.

- 1) *CNN-GRU* [53]: This model leverages CNN, GRU, and FL to tackle the trade-off between data privacy and network security monitoring in a decentralized smart grid environment. The method enhances feature representation and model robustness across diverse datasets. The architectural detail of this model is given in Table 14. In the original work, this model achieves 78.79% ACY in collaborative intrusion detection.
- 2) *PCC_CNN* [54]: This IDS uses a Pearson Correlation Coefficient and Convolutional Neural Network. The architectural detail of this IDS is given in Table 16.

FIGURE 18. Data Directory Structure.

In the original work, PCC_CNN is evaluated on NSL-KDD and Car-Hacking datasets, achieving 97% and 99.93% accuracy, respectively. The system is designed to address security and privacy concerns in transportation IoT for Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs). It utilizes edge devices such as Raspberry Pi and Jetson Xavier for this purpose. However, a key limitation is that the evaluation does not involve any real IoT-specific datasets. This limits the applicability and generalizability of the results to real-world IoT environments.

- 3) *FELIDS* [28]: It is a system designed to provide intrusion detection in the agricultural applications of IoT networks incorporating FL. This approach enables the collaborative training of models without exchanging raw data. *FELIDS* leverages the three distinct DL models, viz., CNN, DNN, and RNN, which are evaluated on three different datasets. Among these, MQTTset is the only dataset specifically tailored for IoT applications. The architectural details of *FELIDS_CNN*, *FELIDS_DNN*, and *FELIDS_RNN* models are given in Table 15. In their experiment,

after completing the final round of FL, all three models demonstrate detection ACY beyond 98% on the MQTTset dataset.

In addition to the above five state-of-the-art FL-based IDSs, we perform an experiment on our FL-MU dataset with a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) model. The architectural detail of the model is summarized in Table 17. Although the FL-MU dataset is primarily focused on experimenting in an FL framework, it can also be used with traditional and non-FL approaches. However, the key difference of employing FL against the traditional or non-FL method is the non-requirement of data sharing or data accumulation to a central point for training the model. Hence, the FL approach preserves data privacy and ensures lower computational cost. Therefore, the limitations of traditional or non-FL approaches are as follows:

- 1) Aggregating data from all clients into a central server compromises data privacy, particularly in real-world IoT environments where the networks are owned by different parties.
- 2) Centralized training often requires high computational resources and memory to process the entire dataset at

once, which is a challenge regarding the large volume and complexity of IoT network traffic.

TABLE 14. Architecture of CNN-GRU model.

Model	Layer Type	Values
CNN-GRU [53]	Convolutional layers	1
	Pooling layers	1 (MaxPooling1D layer)
	Hidden layers	1
	Hidden nodes	128
	GRU layer	1
	GRU_nodes	128
	Dropout	0.5

TABLE 15. Architecture of FELIDS models.

Model	Layer Type	Values
FELIDS_CNN [28]	Convolutional layers	3
	Pooling layers	1 (Global Average Pooling 1D)
	Hidden layers	3
	Hidden nodes	128, 120, 120
	Dropout	0.2
FELIDS_DNN [28]	Hidden layers	2
	Hidden nodes	73
	Dropout	0.1-0.4
FELIDS_RNN [28]	Hidden LSTM layers	3
	Hidden nodes	20, 80, 80
	Dropout	0.2

A. PREPROCESSING

Preprocessing is a fundamental step of Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), which is also a crucial component of ML/DL workflows. This step provides a comprehensive understanding of the dataset to be used for building ML/DL models. On analyzing the FL-MU dataset, 25 features are found to have ‘NaN’ values, and 18 features are found to possess a single unique value, which doesn’t provide additional knowledge relevant to determine the class labels. Those features with missing values, features possessing a single unique value, and remaining features are demonstrated in Table 18, 19, and 20, respectively.

To carry out the validation of the five state-of-the-art FL-based IDSs on the FL-MU dataset, we preprocessed

TABLE 16. Architecture of PCC_CNN model.

Model	Layer Type	Values
PCC_CNN [54]	Convolutional layers	2
	Pooling layers	1 (MaxPooling1D layer)
	Flatten layer	1
	Hidden layers	1
	Hidden nodes	128
	Dropout	0.3

TABLE 17. Architecture of MLP model.

Model	Layer Type	Output Shape	Layer Configuration
Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)	Input	(72,)	Input layer
	Dense	(32,)	32 neurons, ReLU activation
	Dense	(16,)	16 neurons, ReLU activation
	Dense	(8,)	8 neurons, ReLU activation
	Dense (output)	Number of class	Softmax activation
			Optimizer: adam
			Loss: Sparse Categorical Crossentropy

TABLE 18. Features with single unique value.

Features	Datatype	Description
DSCP_UV	int64	DSCP Unique Values
ECN_M	int64	ECN Mode
ECN_UV	int64	ECN Unique Values
ECN_S	int64	ECN Sum
FPC	int64	Fragmented Packet Count
DBytes	int64	Destination Bytes
BIAT	float64	Backward IAT
BackwardPC	int64	Backward Packet Count
BAPS	float64	Backward Average Packet Size
URG_FC	int64	URG Flag Count
ECE_FC	int64	ECE Flag Count
CWR_FC	int64	CWR Flag Count
CE	int64	Checksum Errors
BThroughput	float64	Backward Throughput
BJitter	float64	Backward Jitter
BIPD_Var	float64	Backward Inter-Packet Delay Variance
RTSP_ML	int64	RTSP Methods Lenght
RTSP_MUL	int64	RTSP Methods Unique Lenght

TABLE 19. Features with missing values.

Features	Datatype	Description
BH_M	float64	Backward Header Mode
HTTPRM_M	string	HTTP Request Methods Mode
HTTPGetC	float64	HTTP GET Count
HTTPPutC	float64	HTTP PUT Count
HTTPPostC	float64	HTTP POST Count
HTTPDeletC	float64	HTTP Delete Count
HTTPPatchC	float64	HTTP Patch Count
HTTPHeadC	float64	HTTP Head Count
HTTPOptC	float64	HTTP Option Count
HTTPTraceC	float64	HTTP Trace Count
HTTPConC	float64	HTTP Connect Count
HTTP_SCM	float64	HTTP Status Codes Mode
DNS_QTM	float64	DNS Query Types Mode
DNS_RCM	float64	DNS Response Codes Mode
MQTT_MTM	float64	MQTT Message Types Mode
RTSP_MM	string	RTSP Methods Mode
RTSP_OptionC	float64	RTSP Option Count
RTSP_SETUPC	float64	RTSP Setup Count
RTSP_DESCC	float64	RTSP DESCRIBE Count
RTSP_SPC	float64	RTSP Set parameter Count
RTSP_RecordC	float64	RTSP Record Count
RTSP_TeardownC	float64	RTSP Teardown Count
RTSP_RedirectC	float64	RTSP Redirect Count
RTSP_PlayC	float64	RTSP Play Count
RTSP_PauseC	float64	RTSP Pause Count

each client’s data. The dataset obtained within each client undergoes preprocessing to handle missing values, encode categorical variables, normalize numerical features, and split the dataset into training and testing subsets. The class labels, ‘label’, ‘category’, and ‘type’, are encoded using the LabelEncoder, a module available in the Python Scikit-learn library. A total of 49 features are removed from the original feature set, which includes the identifier features, such as ‘SIP’, ‘DIP’, ‘SPort’, ‘DPort’, ‘SIT’, and ‘STT’, along with the features having a single unique value and those containing missing values. Next, data normalization is performed using the MinMaxScaler module to scale the numerical features

TABLE 20. Description of the remaining features.

Sl. no.	Features	Data type	Description	Sl. no.	Features	Data type	Description
1	FPT	float64	First Packet Time	42	HL_Sum	int64	Header Lengths Sum
2	LPT	float64	Last Packet Time	43	HL_Mode	int64	Header Lengths Mode
3	FD	float64	Flow Duration	44	HL_mean	float64	Header Length Mean
4	FAMin	float64	Flow Active Min	45	SYN_FC	int64	SYN Flag Count
5	FAMean	float64	Flow Active Mean	46	FIN_FC	int64	FIN Flag Count
6	FAMax	float64	Flow Active Max	47	RST_FC	int64	RST Flag Count
7	FAStd	float64	Flow Active Std	48	PSH_FC	int64	PSH Flag Count
8	FIMean	float64	Flow Idle Mean	49	TCP_HD	float64	TCP Handshake Duration
9	FIMin	float64	Flow Idle Min	50	RCcount	int64	Retransmission Count
10	FIMax	float64	Flow Idle Max	51	MPCpackets	int64	Malformed Packets
11	FIStd	float64	Flow Idle Std	52	FThroughput	float64	Forward Throughput
12	DSCP_C	int64	DSCP Count	53	FJitter	float64	Forward Jitter
13	DSCP_M	int64	DSCP Mode	54	FBurst	float64	Flow Burstiness
14	DSCP_S	int64	DSCP Sum	55	FEntropy	float64	Flow Entropy
15	ECN_C	int64	ECN Count	56	PIA_Var	float64	Packet Inter-Arrival Variance
16	TPackets	int64	Total Packets	57	PL	float64	Payload Length
17	TBytes	int64	Total Bytes	58	PEntropy	float64	Payload Entropy
18	SBytes	int64	Source Bytes	59	MP_Count	int64	Multicast Packet Count
19	PLM	int64	Packet Lengths Mode	60	BP_Count	int64	Broadcast Packet Count
20	FI	float64	Flow IAT	61	MGA_L	int64	Multicast Group Address Length
21	FIAT	float64	Forward IAT	62	MGA_UL	int64	Multicast Group Address Unique Length
22	ForwardPC	int64	Forward Packet Count	63	SIT	float64	Session Initiation Time
23	FlowR	float64	Flow Rate	64	STT	float64	Session Termination Time
24	FlowStd	float64	Flow Standard Deviation	65	FIPD_Var	float64	Forward Inter-Packet Delay Variance
25	FlowV	float64	Flow Variance	66	TCPWS_Sum	int64	TCP Window Size Sum
26	FH_M	int64	Forward Header Mode	67	TCPWS_Mean	float64	TCP Window Size Mean
27	FAPS	float64	Forward Average Packet Size	68	TCPWS_Mode	int64	TCP Window Size Mode
28	BAPS	float64	Backward Average Packet Size	69	HTTTPRM_L	int64	HTTP Request Methods Length
29	FBPP	float64	Flow Bytes per Packet	70	HTTTPRM_UL	int64	HTTP Request Methods Unique Length
30	FFD	float64	Forward Flow Duration	71	HTTTP_SCL	int64	HTTP Status Codes Length
31	Proto	int64	Protocol	72	HTTTP_SCUL	int64	HTTP Status Codes Unique Length
32	SIP	str	Source IP	73	DNSQTL	int64	DNS Query Types Length
33	DIP	str	Destination IP	74	DNS_QTUL	int64	DNS Query Types Unique Length
34	SPort	int64	Source Port	75	DNS_RCL	int64	DNS Response Codes Length
35	DPort	int64	Destination Port	76	DNS_Rcul	int64	DNS Response Codes Unique Length
36	SDuration	float64	Session Duration	77	MQTT_MTL	int64	MQTT Message Types Length
37	SPC	int64	Session Packet Count	78	MQTT_MTUL	int64	MQTT Message Types Unique Length
38	SBCcount	int64	Session Byte Count	79	label	str	Label of the traffic
39	BytesPS	float64	Bytes per Second	80	category	str	Category of the traffic
40	PacketsPS	float64	Packets per Second	81	type	str	Type of the traffic
41	RTT	float64	Round Trip Time				

within a specified range [0,1]. Later on, the refined data is split into training and testing sets in a 7:3 ratio.

B. EVALUATION METRICS

Evaluation of the models provides a comprehensive understanding of the model's effectiveness in detecting IoT network intrusions. The six evaluation metrics used to assess the performance of the IDS models are described below.

$$ACY = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

$$PRN = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

$$RCL = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

$$f1 = 2 \times \frac{PRN \times RCL}{PRN + RCL} \quad (4)$$

$$MCC = \frac{TP \times TN - FP \times FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}} \quad (5)$$

$$ASR = \frac{FN}{TP + FN} \quad (6)$$

where TP \rightarrow True Positive, FP \rightarrow False Positive, TN \rightarrow True Negative, and FN \rightarrow False Negative.

The scores and results obtained from the evaluation of the IDS models before the FL round and the final FL rounds are presented in Section IV-C.

C. RESULT ANALYSIS

In this section, we analyze and evaluate the performance of different FL-based DL models on our FL-MU dataset, considering both independent and identically distributed (IID) and non-independent and identically distributed (Non-IID) data scenarios. We consider the five state-of-the-art models, i.e., CNN-GRU, FELIDS_CNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_RNN, and PCC_CNN, on the three FL-MU clients' datasets and validate their effectiveness in identifying different vulnerabilities of IoT networks. Each client initially trained the model for 5 local epochs using the model parameters received from the central server. When a client achieves the maximum ACY of 100% during the initial training phase, i.e., before undergoing the FL training rounds, it is excluded from subsequent FL training rounds. Otherwise, the client continued training up to three FL rounds. The experiments are conducted using three Federated Learning aggregation

TABLE 21. Result obtained at the initial stage of FL for the evaluation on Non-IID data using MLP.

Class	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
Label	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0
Category	C1	1	0.99	0.9969	0.9934	0.9999	0
	C2	0.9993	0.9117	0.8637	0.8811	0.9944	13.63
	C3	0.9998	0.9997	0.9997	0.9997	0.9998	0.03
Type	C1	1	1	0.999	0.9995	1	0
	C2	0.9992	0.7223	0.6977	0.7079	0.9934	30.23
	C3	0.9984	0.9929	0.9897	0.9913	0.9977	1.03

TABLE 22. Result obtained from the final FL round evaluation using FedAvg, FedProx, and FedSGD algorithms for 4-class (category) detection on Non-IID data using an MLP.

Aggregating Algorithm	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
FedAvg	C1	1	0.994	1	0.9969	1	0
	C2	0.9999	0.9893	0.9935	0.9914	0.9996	0.65
	C3	0.9998	0.9997	0.9996	0.9996	0.9997	0.04
FedProx	C1	0.9734	0.6874	0.5155	0.4937	0.8279	48.45
	C2	0.9951	0.7487	0.5219	0.5405	0.9587	47.81
	C3	0.9706	0.9668	0.9465	0.9557	0.958	5.35
FedSGD	C1	0.7956	0.2776	0.3446	0.2842	0.2191	65.54
	C2	0.7829	0.2424	0.4114	0.2254	0.1205	58.86
	C3	0.3974	0.1959	0.3856	0.2544	0.2415	61.44

TABLE 23. Results obtained from the final FL round evaluation using FedAvg, FedProx, and FedSGD algorithms for 5-class (type) detection on Non-IID data using an MLP model.

Aggregating Algorithm	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
FedAvg	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	0.9998	0.7644	0.7953	0.7781	0.9983	20.47
	C3	0.9983	0.9922	0.9905	0.9913	0.9976	0.95
FedProx	C1	0.9938	0.5983	0.5574	0.5753	0.9606	44.26
	C2	0.9949	0.4118	0.4098	0.4106	0.9569	59.02
	C3	0.9494	0.7371	0.763	0.7491	0.9282	23.7
FedSGD	C1	0.9153	0.2288	0.2500	0.2389	0	75.00
	C2	0.9364	0.1873	0.2000	0.1934	0	80.00
	C3	0.3328	0.0666	0.2000	0.0999	0	80.00

algorithms: FedAvg [7], FedProx [55], and FedSGD [7]. Tables 26, 31, 34, and 36 represent the performance metrics obtained before and after the final round of FL training of the five FL models using the FedAvg algorithm, evaluated on non-IID data distribution across the three client datasets. Tables 27, 33, 35, and 39 represent the performance metrics obtained before and after the final round of FL training of the five FL models using the FedAvg algorithm, evaluated on IID data distribution across the three client datasets. From this observation, we found that the models perform better on the non-IID data distribution across all three clients. Therefore, further experiments using FedProx and FedSGD aggregating algorithms are performed only on non-IID data distribution. Tables 28, 29, 32, and 37 represent the performance metrics obtained from the first and final FL training round of the five FL models using the FedProx algorithm, evaluated on non-IID data distribution across the three client datasets. Tables 30 and 38 represent the performance metrics obtained from the final round of FL training of the five FL models using the FedSGD algorithm, evaluated on non-IID data distribution across the three client datasets.

Additionally, we evaluate the performance of the MLP model across all three class labels as shown in Table 21. Initially, the MLP model is executed on the three clients

TABLE 24. Result obtained at the initial stage of FL for the evaluation on Binary (label) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0

TABLE 25. Result obtained at the initial stage of FL for the evaluation on Binary (label) detection on IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0

TABLE 26. Result obtained at the initial stage of FL using FedAvg for 4-class (category) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	0.9996	0.9988	0.9992	1	0.12
	C3	1	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.01
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	1	0.9999	0.9979	0.9989	0.9999	0.21
	C2	1	0.9995	0.9989	0.9992	0.9999	0.11
	C3	0.9990	0.9990	0.9982	0.9986	0.9986	0.18
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	0.9999	1	1	0.01
	C3	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.01
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	1	0.01
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0

without federated training, and its performance is recorded. Next, the same MLP model is executed for federated training, and the results are recorded for a fair comparison. Table 22 presents the results of the MLP model obtained after the final round of federated training during 4-class attack detection and comparing three FL aggregation algorithms across all three clients. Similarly, Table 23 presents the MLP results obtained after the final round of federated training during 5-class attack detection and comparing three FL aggregation algorithms across all three clients. The performance of the models prior to FL rounds is summarized in Tables 24, 25, 26, 27, 31, and 33 corresponding to the detection of the ‘label’ (binary), ‘category’ (multiclass), and

TABLE 27. Result obtained at the initial stage of FL using FedAvg for 7-class (category) detection on IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	1	0.9996	0.9988	0.9992	1	0.51
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0.57
	C3	1	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.73
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9993	0.9951	0.9902	0.9926	0.9971	0.98
	C2	0.9992	0.9954	0.9892	0.9922	0.9971	1.08
	C3	0.9968	0.8369	0.8408	0.8387	0.9877	15.92
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9991	0.9922	0.9939	0.993	0.9966	0.61
	C2	0.9992	0.9936	0.9944	0.994	0.9969	0.56
	C3	0.9992	0.9934	0.9935	0.9934	0.9967	0.65
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9991	0.9925	0.9936	0.993	0.993	0.64
	C2	0.999	0.9864	0.9931	0.9897	0.9962	0.69
	C3	0.999	0.9924	0.9922	0.9923	0.9959	0.78
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.9995	0.9965	0.9959	0.9962	0.9962	0.41
	C2	0.9995	0.9961	0.9956	0.9959	0.9979	0.44
	C3	0.9995	0.9965	0.9957	0.9961	0.9979	0.43

TABLE 28. Results obtained at the initial stage of FL using FedProx for 4-class (category) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	0.9716	0.4554	0.4999	0.4759	0.8105	50.01
	C2	0.9615	0.4901	0.3566	0.3566	0.3566	64.34
	C3	0.9384	0.9341	0.8857	0.9036	0.9123	11.43
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9148	0.2287	0.25	0.2389	0	75.00
	C2	0.9368	0.2342	0.25	0.2418	0	75.00
	C3	0.3829	0.0957	0.25	0.1384	0	75.00
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9831	0.7455	0.6022	0.6428	0.8898	39.78
	C2	0.9812	0.4951	0.4414	0.4643	0.8299	55.86
	C3	0.924	0.9227	0.8562	0.8782	0.8923	14.38
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9148	0.2287	0.25	0.2389	0	75.00
	C2	0.9368	0.2342	0.25	0.2418	0	75.00
	C3	0.8909	0.8658	0.8403	0.8105	0.8549	15.97
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.9648	0.4817	0.47	0.4753	0.7554	53.00
	C2	0.9515	0.4877	0.3134	0.3448	0.4703	68.66
	C3	0.9526	0.9471	0.9122	0.9261	0.9325	8.78

TABLE 29. Results obtained from the final FL round using FedProx for 4-class (category) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	0.9836	0.6966	0.6087	0.6267	0.896	39.13
	C2	0.9954	0.7485	0.5356	0.5618	0.9605	46.44
	C3	0.9681	0.9622	0.9494	0.9544	0.9549	5.06
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9148	0.2287	0.25	0.2389	0	75.00
	C2	0.9368	0.2342	0.25	0.2418	0	75.00
	C3	0.3829	0.0957	0.25	0.1384	0	75.00
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9777	0.9412	0.6003	0.6365	0.8568	39.97
	C2	0.9962	0.7306	0.6045	0.6443	0.9673	39.55
	C3	0.9519	0.9454	0.9061	0.9207	0.9317	9.39
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9924	0.7202	0.7011	0.7103	0.9517	29.89
	C2	0.9934	0.4982	0.4939	0.4960	0.9429	50.61
	C3	0.9833	0.9833	0.9706	0.9766	0.9761	2.94
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.9915	0.9768	0.6786	0.699	0.9462	32.14
	C2	0.997	0.7173	0.6319	0.664	0.9742	36.81
	C3	0.9759	0.9736	0.9568	0.9646	0.9656	4.32

‘type’ (multiclass) targets, respectively. While Tables 28 and 32 present the result obtained from the first round of FL training using FedProx aggregating algorithm, corresponding to ‘category’ (multiclass), and ‘type’ (multiclass) targets, respectively. Tables 29, 30, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, and 39 present the performance after the final FL rounds for the ‘category’ and ‘type’ attack detection tasks. Since the binary ‘label’ class consistently achieved 100% ACY in the initial training phase, as shown in Tables 24 and 25, it was excluded from the FL training rounds. Additionally, the C1, C2, and C3 represent the FL Client 1, Client 2, and Client 3, respectively. From the experimental analysis, it is clearly observed that the models yield 100% ACY and 0% ASR, as shown in Tables 24 and 25, in both IID and Non-IID data scenarios, which indicates

TABLE 30. Result obtained from the final FL round using FedSGD for 4-class (category) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	0.7407	0.2662	0.3283	0.2618	0.1556	67.17
	C2	0.7271	0.2403	0.3756	0.2152	0.0812	62.44
	C3	0.2846	0.1226	0.2324	0.1603	0.0241	76.76
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.1124	0.1857	0.2180	0.0526	-0.1352	78.20
	C2	0.1135	0.1930	0.1060	0.0526	-0.1542	89.40
	C3	0.0708	0.0369	0.0964	0.0485	-0.2372	90.36
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9154	0.2289	0.2500	0.2390	0	75.00
	C2	0.9378	0.2345	0.2500	0.2420	0	75.00
	C3	0.3394	0.0849	0.2500	0.1267	0	75.00
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9182	0.2295	0.2500	0.2393	0	75.00
	C2	0.9371	0.2343	0.2500	0.2419	0	75.00
	C3	0.3400	0.0850	0.2500	0.1269	0	75.00
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.1374	0.1906	0.1548	0.0668	-0.2404	84.52
	C2	0.1115	0.1941	0.1887	0.0516	-0.1379	81.13
	C3	0.0938	0.0469	0.1079	0.0623	-0.2538	89.21

TABLE 31. Result obtained at the initial stage of FL using FedAvg for 5-class (type) detection on Non-IID evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	1	0.9985	0.9987	0.9986	1	0.13
	C2	0.9999	0.9290	0.9695	0.9467	0.9994	3.05
	C3	0.9987	0.9924	0.9954	0.9939	0.9982	0.46
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9997	0.7994	0.7980	0.7987	0.9994	20.2
	C2	0.9999	0.7940	0.7983	0.7961	0.9989	20.17
	C3	0.9984	0.9935	0.9893	0.9914	0.9977	1.07
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	1	0.9985	0.9969	0.9977	1	0.31
	C2	0.9999	0.9197	0.9929	0.9599	0.9995	0.71
	C3	0.9955	0.9904	0.9855	0.9879	0.9936	1.45
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9997	0.7668	0.7943	0.7795	0.9994	20.57
	C2	0.9999	0.7945	0.8000	0.7972	0.9999	20.0
	C3	0.5131	0.6378	0.3692	0.3303	0.3459	7.83
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	1	0.9998	0.9987	0.9992	1	0.13
	C2	0.9999	0.9516	0.9499	0.9508	0.9995	5.01
	C3	0.9991	0.9942	0.9965	0.9953	0.9987	0.35

TABLE 32. Results obtained at the initial stage of FL using FedProx for 5-class (type) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	0.9668	0.3928	0.3829	0.3874	0.7711	61.71
	C2	0.9615	0.3921	0.2853	0.3156	0.6133	71.47
	C3	0.8712	0.6532	0.669	0.6388	0.8228	33.10
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9148	0.183	0.2	0.1911	0	80.00
	C2	0.9368	0.1874	0.2	0.1935	0	80.00
	C3	0.3829	0.0766	0.2	0.1108	0	80.00
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9148	0.183	0.2	0.1911	0	80.00
	C2	0.9378	0.3876	0.2034	0.2003	0.1214	79.66
	C3	0.8504	0.6827	0.5655	0.5517	0.7886	43.45
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9148	0.183	0.2	0.1911	0	80.00
	C2	0.9368	0.1874	0.2000	0.1935	0	80.00
	C3	0.3363	0.2673	0.2	0.1007	0.0038	80.00
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.97	0.3829	0.3944	0.3886	0.7963	60.56
	C2	0.985	0.3969	0.3663	0.38	0.8668	63.37
	C3	0.9392	0.7466	0.7453	0.745	0.9136	25.47

that the network traffic patterns corresponding to legitimate and malicious behavior in the FL-MU dataset are clearly distinguishable. However, as shown in Tables 36 and 39, the performance of the models degrades in the multiclass detection tasks, especially for the 4-class, 5-class detection under the Non-IID distribution and 7-class, 12-class detection under the IID distribution, respectively. The lower f1 and MCC scores observed in these settings are primarily due to the highly imbalanced nature of the dataset, which impairs the models’ ability to correctly classify underrepresented classes. Additionally, a high value of the average ASR scores indicates high misclassification before the FL rounds of training as shown in Tables 26, 27, 28, 31, 32, and 33 while a low value of the average ASR scores after the final

TABLE 33. Result obtained at the initial stage of FL using FedAvg for 12-class (type) detection on IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	0.9977	0.8267	0.8501	0.8343	0.991	26.23
	C2	0.998	0.9178	0.8692	0.8811	0.9922	26.26
	C3	0.9976	0.8501	0.8265	0.832	0.9905	24.06
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9963	0.6968	0.6972	0.694	0.9857	30.29
	C2	0.9972	0.7286	0.7107	0.7114	0.989	28.93
	C3	0.9965	0.6969	0.7089	0.7013	0.9863	29.11
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9973	0.7921	0.7916	0.7791	0.9895	20.84
	C2	0.9972	0.7328	0.7856	0.7437	0.9891	21.44
	C3	0.9968	0.795	0.7657	0.7709	0.9875	23.41
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9823	0.5446	0.5297	0.5207	0.9296	47.03
	C2	0.9961	0.7743	0.7276	0.7321	0.9846	27.24
	C3	0.983	0.5437	0.5337	0.5252	0.9327	46.63
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.9977	0.8267	0.8501	0.8343	0.991	14.99
	C2	0.998	0.9178	0.8692	0.8811	0.9922	13.08
	C3	0.9976	0.8501	0.8265	0.832	0.9905	17.41

TABLE 34. Result obtained from the final FL round using FedAvg for 4-class (category) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0.00
	C2	1	0.9990	0.9979	0.9985	0.9999	0.21
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0.01
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0.00
	C2	1	0.9998	0.9993	0.9996	1	0.07
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0.00
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0.00
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0.01
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0.01
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0.00
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0.00
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0.01
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	1	1	1	1	1	0.00
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0.00
	C3	1	1	1	1	1	0.00

TABLE 35. Result obtained from the final FL round using FedAvg for 7-class (category) detection on IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	0.9994	0.995	0.9943	0.9947	0.9975	0.55
	C2	1	1	1	1	1	0.57
	C3	0.9994	0.9962	0.9941	0.9951	0.9975	0.59
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9993	0.9957	0.9943	0.995	0.9974	0.57
	C2	0.9994	0.9953	0.995	0.9952	0.9975	0.50
	C3	0.9993	0.9955	0.9933	0.9943	0.9972	0.67
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9994	0.9955	0.9952	0.9954	0.9976	0.48
	C2	0.9992	0.9937	0.9947	0.9941	0.9969	0.53
	C3	0.9992	0.9943	0.9944	0.9943	0.9971	0.56
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9992	0.9938	0.9943	0.994	0.9968	0.57
	C2	0.9992	0.9938	0.9943	0.9941	0.9968	0.57
	C3	0.9992	0.9939	0.9944	0.9941	0.9969	0.56
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.9995	0.9966	0.9961	0.9964	0.9981	0.39
	C2	0.9995	0.9967	0.9956	0.9961	0.998	0.44
	C3	0.9994	0.9965	0.9952	0.9958	0.9978	0.48

FL rounds of training indicates lower misclassification as shown in Tables 29, 34, 35, 36, 37, and 39. Additionally, Table 21 shows the result obtained before undergoing FL rounds of training using MLP. On undergoing three rounds of FL training, the models’ performance degrades while aggregating using FedProx and FedSGD as compared to FedAvg as evident in Tables 22, and 23. However, the model’s performance is inconsistent and extremely degraded with the FedSGD aggregating algorithm when evaluated on other methods available in the literature [56]. The same statistics are also observed in our experiment using the FedSGD algorithm as reported in Tables 30, and 38 due to the imbalanced distribution of the Client’s data.

Moreover, when we evaluate the CNN-GRU, PCC_CNN models, FELIDS_CNN, FELIDS_DNN, and FELIDS_RNN on our FL-MU dataset, we observe that these models

TABLE 36. Result obtained from the final FL round using FedAvg for 5-class (type) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	1	0.9998	0.9987	0.9992	1	0.13
	C2	1	0.9637	0.9943	0.9775	0.9997	0.57
	C3	0.9991	0.9941	0.9969	0.9955	0.9988	0.31
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	1	0.9997	0.9965	0.9981	0.9999	0.35
	C2	0.9999	0.7942	0.7987	0.7964	0.9989	20.13
	C3	0.9984	0.9960	0.9907	0.9933	0.9982	0.93
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	1	0.9972	0.9982	0.9977	1	0.18
	C2	0.9999	0.9751	0.867	0.8957	0.9993	13.3
	C3	0.9984	0.9930	0.9899	0.9914	0.9977	1.01
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9997	0.7675	0.8000	0.7823	0.9995	20
	C2	0.9999	0.7945	0.8000	0.7972	0.9990	20
	C3	0.9767	0.7584	0.8000	0.7768	0.9676	20
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	1	0.9998	0.9987	0.9992	1	0.13
	C2	0.9999	0.9691	0.8704	0.8984	0.9993	12.96
	C3	0.9993	0.9961	0.9964	0.9963	0.9900	0.36

TABLE 37. Result obtained from the final FL round using FedProx for 5-class (type) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	0.9963	0.5988	0.5752	0.5862	0.9767	42.48
	C2	0.9948	0.3972	0.4	0.3986	0.9553	60.00
	C3	0.9507	0.7522	0.7581	0.7541	0.9301	24.19
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9148	0.183	0.2	0.1911	0	80.00
	C2	0.9368	0.1874	0.2	0.1935	0	80.00
	C3	0.3829	0.0766	0.2	0.1108	0	80.00
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9813	0.596	0.4686	0.5003	0.8768	53.14
	C2	0.9918	0.3979	0.3899	0.3938	0.9294	61.01
	C3	0.9245	0.7364	0.7196	0.7256	0.893	28.04
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9944	0.5831	0.5706	0.5767	0.9642	42.94
	C2	0.9926	0.3984	0.3926	0.3955	0.9365	60.74
	C3	0.9640	0.7482	0.7837	0.7633	0.9495	21.63
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.9945	0.585	0.5693	0.5769	0.9649	43.07
	C2	0.9937	0.5972	0.3964	0.3968	0.9461	60.36
	C3	0.9608	0.7616	0.7741	0.767	0.9446	22.59

TABLE 38. Result obtained from the final FL round using FedSGD for 5-class (type) detection on Non-IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	0.9184	0.1879	0.2000	0.1938	0.2513	60.00
	C2	0.9516	0.3808	0.2531	0.2782	0.4833	74.69
	C3	0.3412	0.0792	0.2064	0.1142	0.1028	79.36
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9126	0.2282	0.2500	0.2386	0.0000	75.00
	C2	0.9381	0.1876	0.2000	0.1936	0.0000	80.00
	C3	0.3391	0.0678	0.2000	0.1013	0.0000	80.00
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9187	0.1837	0.2000	0.1915	0	80.00
	C2	0.9353	0.1871	0.2000	0.1933	0	80.00
	C3	0.3345	0.0669	0.2000	0.1003	0	80.00
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9175	0.1835	0.2000	0.1914	0	80.00
	C2	0.9406	0.1881	0.2000	0.1939	0	80.00
	C3	0.3346	0.0669	0.2000	0.1003	0	80.00
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.9185	0.4797	0.2509	0.2412	0.0431	74.91
	C2	0.9352	0.1871	0.2000	0.1933	0.0328	80.00
	C3	0.3337	0.1855	0.2006	0.1014	0.0174	79.94

demonstrate improve performance with binary detection, achieving higher scores compared to their original evaluations, as shown in Tables 40, 41, 42, 43, and 44. This indicates that these models perform better on the FL-MU dataset on binary detection. However, the models’ performance declines in the multiclass detection task. This outcome highlights a key limitation of the models in handling data imbalance, which is a common challenge in IoT network intrusion datasets. These findings emphasize the need for future research focused on developing or integrating techniques to mitigate the effects of data imbalance within FL-based intrusion detection systems.

Furthermore, the models exhibit slightly higher performance under the Non-IID distribution than the IID distribution. This is due to the fact that, in the Non-IID distribution, local models learn more discriminative features specific to those classes. When these specialized local model

TABLE 39. Result obtained after final FL round using FedAvg for 12-class (type) detection on IID data, evaluated across CNN-GRU, FELIDS_RNN, FELIDS_DNN, FELIDS_CNN, and PCC_CNN.

Model	Client	ACY	PRN	RCL	f1	MCC	Average ASR (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	C1	0.9974	0.7317	0.7522	0.7381	0.99	24.78
	C2	0.9975	0.7181	0.713	0.7108	0.9902	28.70
	C3	0.9973	0.734	0.7561	0.7409	0.9895	24.39
FELIDS_CNN [28]	C1	0.9968	0.7029	0.7047	0.6998	0.9875	29.53
	C2	0.9971	0.7106	0.7073	0.7052	0.9886	29.27
	C3	0.997	0.7134	0.7027	0.7026	0.9883	29.73
FELIDS_DNN [28]	C1	0.9966	0.8482	0.8883	0.8615	0.9866	18.31
	C2	0.9969	0.7803	0.787	0.7788	0.9879	19.63
	C3	0.9965	0.7752	0.7261	0.7312	0.9863	19.94
FELIDS_RNN [28]	C1	0.9973	0.8463	0.8667	0.8464	0.9893	13.33
	C2	0.9969	0.7813	0.7402	0.7428	0.9878	25.99
	C3	0.9972	0.799	0.7762	0.7784	0.9892	22.38
PCC_CNN [54]	C1	0.9976	0.7804	0.8094	0.7891	0.9908	19.06
	C2	0.9978	0.8829	0.8874	0.8657	0.9916	11.26
	C3	0.9977	0.8628	0.8709	0.8634	0.9911	12.90

TABLE 40. Comparison of accuracy scores from binary detection on the FL-MU and NSL-KDD datasets using the CNN-GRU model.

Models	Dataset	Accuracy (%)
CNN-GRU [53]	NSL-KDD	89.19
	FL-MU (Client 1)	100
	FL-MU (Client 2)	100
	FL-MU (Client 3)	100

TABLE 41. Comparison of accuracy scores from binary detection among the FL-MU dataset, NSL-KDD, and Car-hacking dataset using the PCC_CNN model.

Models	Dataset	Accuracy (%)
PCC_CNN [54]	NSL-KDD	97.08
	Car-hacking	99.72
	FL-MU (Client 1)	100
	FL-MU (Client 2)	100
	FL-MU (Client 3)	100

TABLE 42. Comparison of accuracy scores from binary detection among the FL-MU, IDS2018, MQTTset, and InSDN datasets using the FELIDS_CNN model.

Models	Dataset	Accuracy (%)
FELIDS_CNN [28]	IDS2018 non-IID	91.42
	IDS2018 IID	94.09
	MQTTset non-IID	83.03
	MQTTset IID	85.35
	InSDN non-IID	99.02
	InSDN IID	99.73
	FL-MU (C1)	100
	FL-MU (C2)	100
	FL-MU (C3)	100

TABLE 43. Comparison of accuracy scores from binary detection among the FL-MU, IDS2018, MQTTset, and InSDN datasets using the FELIDS_DNN model.

Models	Dataset	Accuracy (%)
FELIDS_DNN [28]	IDS2018 non-IID	86.43
	IDS2018 IID	93.29
	MQTTset non-IID	83.52
	MQTTset IID	87.23
	InSDN non-IID	94.80
	InSDN IID	97.80
	FL-MU (Client 1)	100
	FL-MU (Client 2)	100
	FL-MU (Client 3)	100

updates are aggregated, a more generalized global model is obtained. However, the significant class imbalance issue across the clients of the IID case leads to underfitting of the model, which eventually degrades the performance of the global model.

TABLE 44. Comparison of accuracy scores from binary detection among the FL-MU, IDS2018, MQTTset, and InSDN datasets using the FELI_RNN model.

Models	Dataset	Accuracy (%)
FELIDS_RNN [28]	IDS2018 non-IID	93.97
	IDS2018 IID	94.15
	MQTTset non-IID	77.07
	MQTTset IID	88.13
	InSDN non-IID	95.30
	InSDN IID	94.75
	FL-MU (Client 1)	100
	FL-MU (Client 2)	100
	FL-MU (Client 3)	100

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The FL-MU dataset was developed at the Manipur University cybersecurity lab, which provides a significant contribution to the research community. The network testbed used to create the FL-MU dataset consists of three FL clients. Special care has been taken to ensure that the network traffic is not mixed with the global network traffic. The FL-MU dataset includes network traffic from various IoT communication protocols, such as AMQP, COAP, DDS, MQTT, SOAP, STOMP, and WebSocket, along with IoT communication-based attacks. It includes a good number of attack scenarios that are mostly ignored in the existing benchmark datasets. The new attack types included in our dataset are Sinkhole, Sybil, Slowite, and IoT protocol-based flooding attacks like MQTT connect flooding, AMQP flooding, STOMP flooding, and SOAP flooding. Another major advantage of the dataset is that it contains network traffic in raw and pre-processed forms. Researchers can develop their own IDSs and validate their systems using the FL-MU dataset. Further, we establish the effectiveness of the dataset using recent FL-based IDSs, considering both IID and Non-IID data distributions, and observe promising results. The dataset creates a new paradigm to enhance security features on FL-based IDS. It fulfills the limitations of existing datasets by incorporating new variants of attack types. Moreover, the FL-MU dataset would help IoT security researchers in exploring protocol-specific IoT communication attacks. The experimental analysis has shown the validation of the FL-MU dataset across various existing DL-based IDS models in an FL approach. The ability of the FL-MU dataset can be further enhanced by applying appropriate feature selection methods and more in-depth data preprocessing. Future work of this study will focus on developing and validating robust FL-based IDSs using the FL-MU dataset, with an emphasis on leveraging an effective feature selection method.

DECLARATION

No ethical and data privacy concerns are required for this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. H. Mahdi and A. A. Abdullah, "Fortifying future IoT security: A comprehensive review on lightweight post-quantum cryptography," *Eng., Technol. Appl. Sci. Res.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 21812–21821, Apr. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://mail.etasr.com/index.php/ETASR/article/view/10141>

- [2] A. Padthe, R. Ashtagi, S. Mohite, P. Gaikwad, R. Bidwe, and H. M. Naveen, "Harnessing federated learning for efficient analysis of large-scale healthcare image datasets in IoT-enabled healthcare systems," *Int. J. Intell. Syst. Appl. Eng.*, vol. 12, no. 10s, pp. 253–263, Jan. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ijisae.org/index.php/IJISAE/article/view/4374>
- [3] U. B. Clinton, N. Hoque, S. Raza, and M. Bhuyan, "Securing IoT: Unveiling attacks with multiview-multitask learning," *IEEE Trans. Artif. Intell.*, early access, Oct. 1, 2025, doi: 10.1109/TAI.2025.3615565.
- [4] F. Shaheen, B. Verma, and M. Asafuddoula, "Impact of automatic feature extraction in deep learning architecture," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Digit. Image Comput., Techn. Appl. (DICTA)*, Nov. 2016, pp. 1–8.
- [5] F. De Keersmaecker, Y. Cao, G. K. Ndonga, and R. Sadre, "A survey of public IoT datasets for network security research," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 1808–1840, 3rd Quart., 2023.
- [6] S. S. Alsaleh, M. El Bachir Menai, and S. Al-Ahmadi, "Federated learning-based model to lightweight IDSs for heterogeneous IoT networks: State-of-the-art, challenges, and future directions," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 134256–134272, 2024.
- [7] H. B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, S. Hampson, and B. A. Y. Arcas, "Communication-efficient learning of deep networks from decentralized data," in *Proc. 20th Int. Conf. Artif. Intell. Statist.*, Apr. 2016, pp. 1273–1282.
- [8] I. Vaccari, G. Chiola, M. Aiello, M. Mongelli, and E. Cambiaso, "MQTTset, a new dataset for machine learning techniques on MQTT," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 22, p. 6578, Nov. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/20/22/6578>
- [9] U. B. Clinton and N. Hoque, "MU-IoT: A new IoT intrusion dataset for network and application layer attacks analysis," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 166068–166092, 2024.
- [10] A. R. Gad, A. A. Nashat, and T. M. Barkat, "Intrusion detection system using machine learning for vehicular ad hoc networks based on ToN-IoT dataset," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 142206–142217, 2021.
- [11] N. Koroniotis, N. Moustafa, E. Sitnikova, and B. Turnbull, "Towards the development of realistic botnet dataset in the Internet of Things for network forensic analytics: Bot-IoT dataset," *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 100, pp. 779–796, Nov. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X18327687>
- [12] A. Alsaedi, N. Moustafa, Z. Tari, A. Mahmood, and A. Anwar, "TON_IoT telemetry dataset: A new generation dataset of IoT and IIoT for data-driven intrusion detection systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 165130–165150, 2020.
- [13] M. A. Ferrag, O. Friha, D. Hamouda, L. Maglaras, and H. Janicke, "Edge-IIoTset: A new comprehensive realistic cyber security dataset of IoT and IIoT applications for centralized and federated learning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 40281–40306, 2022.
- [14] A. Alatrani, L. F. Sikos, M. Johnstone, P. Szweczyk, and J. J. Kang, "DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT: A dataset for evaluating intrusions in IoT networks using the MQTT protocol," *Comput. Netw.*, vol. 231, Jul. 2023, Art. no. 109809. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128623002542>
- [15] P. Kumar, J. Liu, A. S. Md Tayeen, S. Misra, H. Cao, J. Harikumar, and O. Perez, "FLNET2023: Realistic network intrusion detection dataset for federated learning," in *Proc. IEEE Mil. Commun. Conf. (MILCOM)*, Oct. 2023, pp. 345–350.
- [16] E. C. P. Neto, S. Dadkhah, R. Ferreira, A. Zohourian, R. Lu, and A. A. Ghorbani, "CICIoT2023: A real-time dataset and benchmark for large-scale attacks in IoT environment," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 13, p. 5941, Jun. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/23/13/5941>
- [17] S. Dadkhah, E. C. P. Neto, R. Ferreira, R. C. Molokwu, S. Sadeghi, and A. A. Ghorbani, "CICIoMT2024: A benchmark dataset for multi-protocol security assessment in IoMT," *Internet Things*, vol. 28, Dec. 2024, Art. no. 101351. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2542660524002920>
- [18] A. A. R. A. Omar, B. Soudan, and A. Altaweel, "UOS_IOTSH_2024: A comprehensive network traffic dataset for sinkhole attacks in diverse RPL IoT networks," *Data Brief*, vol. 55, Aug. 2024, Art. no. 110650. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352340924006176>
- [19] R. Ferreira, I. Bispo, C. Rabadão, L. Santos, and R. L. D. C. Costa, "Farm-flow dataset: Intrusion detection in smart agriculture based on network flows," *Comput. Electr. Eng.*, vol. 121, Jan. 2025, Art. no. 109892. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0045790624008188>
- [20] J. A. Adjei, N. Zincir-Heywood, M. Heywood, B. Nandy, and N. Seddigh, "Can flow metadata based signatures generalize for identifying attacks on IoT devices?" in *Proc. NOMS-IEEE Netw. Operations Manage. Symp.*, May 2025, pp. 1–5.
- [21] S. Alosaimi and S. M. Almutairi, "An intrusion detection system using BoT-IoT," *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 13, no. 9, p. 5427, Apr. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/13/9/5427>
- [22] M. Zeeshan, Q. Riaz, M. A. Bilal, M. K. Shahzad, H. Jabeen, S. A. Haider, and A. Rahim, "Protocol-based deep intrusion detection for DoS and DDoS attacks using UNSW-NB15 and bot-IoT data-sets," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 2269–2283, 2022.
- [23] M. Shafiq, Z. Tian, A. K. Bashir, X. Du, and M. Guizani, "CorrAUC: A malicious bot-IoT traffic detection method in IoT network using machine-learning techniques," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3242–3254, Mar. 2021.
- [24] J. L. Leevy, J. Hancock, T. M. Khoshgoftaar, and J. Peterson, "Detecting information theft attacks in the bot-IoT dataset," in *Proc. 20th IEEE Int. Conf. Mach. Learn. Appl. (ICMLA)*, Dec. 2021, pp. 807–812.
- [25] A. Sharma and H. Babbar, "BoT-IoT: Detection of DDoS attacks in Internet of Things for smart cities," in *Proc. 10th Int. Conf. Comput. Sustain. Global Develop. (INDIACom)*, Mar. 2023, pp. 438–443.
- [26] A. R. Gad, M. A. Haggag, A. A. Nashat, and T. M. Barakat, "A distributed intrusion detection system using machine learning for IoT based on ToN-IoT dataset," *Int. J. Adv. Comput. Sci. Appl.*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 1–16, 2022, doi: 10.14569/ijacsa.2022.0130667.
- [27] L. Takhellambam, U. B. Clinton, Y. R. Singh, C. Chandam, K. R. Singh, and N. Hoque, "IoT network intrusion detection using federated learning," in *Proc. NIELIT's Int. Conf. Commun.*, 2024, pp. 325–339.
- [28] O. Friha, M. A. Ferrag, L. Shu, L. Maglaras, K.-K.-R. Choo, and M. Nafaa, "FELIDS: Federated learning-based intrusion detection system for agricultural Internet of Things," *J. Parallel Distrib. Comput.*, vol. 165, pp. 17–31, Jul. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0743731522000570>
- [29] V. Hnamte and J. Hussain, "DCNNBiLSTM: An efficient hybrid deep learning-based intrusion detection system," *Telematics Inform. Rep.*, vol. 10, Jun. 2023, Art. no. 100053. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2772503023000130>
- [30] A. Babu and A. Bagubali, "Federated learning with sailfish-optimized ensemble models for anomaly detection in IoT edge computing environment," *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 53171–53187, 2025.
- [31] M. M. Khan and M. Alkhatami, "Anomaly detection in IoT-based healthcare: Machine learning for enhanced security," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 5872, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1038/s41598-024-56126-x.
- [32] A. I. Jony and A. K. B. Arnob, "A long short-term memory based approach for detecting cyber attacks in IoT using CIC-IoT2023 dataset," *J. Edge Comput.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 28–42, May 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://acncsci.org/journal/index.php/jec/article/view/648>
- [33] M. Belkheir, M. Rouissat, A. Mokaddem, D. Ziani, and P. Lorenz, "Lightweight novel approach for collaborative packet-based mitigation of blackhole attacks in RPL-based IoT," *J. Netw. Syst. Manage.*, vol. 33, no. 2, p. 34, Apr. 2025, doi: 10.1007/s10922-025-09908-1.
- [34] J. A. Adjei, N. Zincir-Heywood, M. Heywood, N. Seddigh, and B. Nandy, "DALHOUSIE NIMS LAB IoT ATTACK DATASET 2025-1," Dalhousie Univ., Halifax, NS, USA, Tech. Rep., Jan. 2025, doi: 10.21227/vrwj-bc48.
- [35] N. Naik, "Choice of effective messaging protocols for IoT systems: MQTT, CoAP, AMQP and HTTP," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Syst. Eng. Symp. (ISSE)*, Oct. 2017, pp. 1–7.
- [36] A. Corsaro, "The data distribution service tutorial," ZettaScale Technol., Saint Aubin-France, Tech. Rep., 2014.
- [37] P. K. Donta, S. N. Srirama, T. Amgoth, and C. S. R. Annavarapu, "Survey on recent advances in IoT application layer protocols and machine learning scope for research directions," *Digit. Commun. Netw.*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 727–744, Oct. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352864821000845>
- [38] D. Soni and A. Makwana, "A survey on MQTT: A protocol of Internet of Things (IoT)," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Telecommun., Power Anal. Comput. Techn. (ICTPACT)*, vol. 20, 2017, pp. 173–177.
- [39] J. A. Jovita, G. Ramachandran, and N. E. Rathinam, "REST API and SOAP-Web services validation in IoT environment," *NeuroQuantology*, vol. 20, no. 16, p. 695, 2022.
- [40] D. E. Ouadghiri, B. Aghoutane, and N. E. Farissi, "Communication model in the Internet of Things," *Proc. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 177, pp. 72–77, Jan. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S187705092032278X>

- [41] N. Hoque, M. H. Bhuyan, R. C. Baishya, D. K. Bhattacharyya, and J. K. Kalita, "Network attacks: Taxonomy, tools and systems," *J. Neww. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 40, pp. 307–324, Apr. 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1084804513001756>
- [42] N. Hoque, D. K. Bhattacharyya, and J. K. Kalita, "Botnet in DDoS attacks: Trends and challenges," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 2242–2270, 4th Quart., 2015.
- [43] I. Vaccari, M. Aiello, and E. Cambiaso, "SlowITe, a novel denial of service attack affecting MQTT," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 10, p. 2932, May 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/20/10/2932>
- [44] M. El-Hajj and D. Vorotilov, "Testing the security and performance of MQTT protocol on raspberry pi for IoT applications," in *Proc. IEEE Asia-Pacific Conf. Wireless Mobile (APWiMob)*, Nov. 2024, pp. 67–72.
- [45] A. Mallik, "Man-in-the-middle-attack: Understanding in simple words," *Cyberspace, Jurnal Pendidikan Teknologi Informatika*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 109–134, Jan. 2019.
- [46] S. Luo, Y. Lai, and J. Liu, "Selective forwarding attack detection and network recovery mechanism based on cloud-edge cooperation in software-defined wireless sensor network," *Comput. Secur.*, vol. 126, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 103083.
- [47] A. Hariri, N. Giannelos, and B. Arief, "Selective forwarding attack on IoT home security kits," in *Proc. Comput. Secur., ESORICS Int. Workshops*, Sep. 2020, pp. 360–373.
- [48] G. Jahandoust and F. Ghassemi, "An adaptive sinkhole aware algorithm in wireless sensor networks," *Ad Hoc Netw.*, vol. 59, pp. 24–34, May 2017.
- [49] Z. Huang, S. Liu, X. Mao, K. Chen, and J. Li, "Insight of the protection for data security under selective opening attacks," *Inf. Sci.*, vols. 412–413, pp. 223–241, Oct. 2017.
- [50] Y. Liu, M. Ma, X. Liu, N. N. Xiong, A. Liu, and Y. Zhu, "Design and analysis of probing route to defense sink-hole attacks for Internet of Things security," *IEEE Trans. Netw. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 356–372, Jan. 2020.
- [51] J. R. Douceur, "The Sybil attack," in *Proc. 1st Int. Workshop Peer-Peer Syst.*, 2002, pp. 251–260.
- [52] J. Newsome, E. Shi, D. Song, and A. Perrig, "The Sybil attack in sensor networks: Analysis & defenses," in *Proc. 3rd Int. Symp. Inf. Process. Sensor Netw.*, Apr. 2004, pp. 259–268, doi: 10.1145/984622.984660.
- [53] F. Zhai, T. Yang, H. Chen, B. He, and S. Li, "Intrusion detection method based on CNN-GRU-FL in a smart grid environment," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 5, p. 1164, Feb. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/12/5/1164>
- [54] M. H. Bhavsar, Y. B. Bekele, K. Roy, J. C. Kelly, and D. Limbrick, "FL-IDS: Federated learning-based intrusion detection system using edge devices for transportation IoT," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 52215–52226, 2024.
- [55] T. Li, A. K. Sahu, M. Zaheer, M. Sanjabi, A. Talwalkar, and V. Smith, "Federated optimization in heterogeneous networks," in *Proc. Mach. Learn. Syst.*, 2018, pp. 429–450.
- [56] P. Kumar Singh, A. Chowdhury, and A. Pal, "Distributed anomaly detection using federated learning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 150426–150437, 2025.

URIKHIMBAM BOBY CLINTON received the Master of Computer Applications (M.C.A.) degree from the Department of Computer Science, Manipur University, Canchipur, Imphal, Manipur, India, in 2021, where he is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree. Since 2022, he has been a Junior Research Fellow on a fully government-funded project. He has contributed to the field through 11 research publications. His research interests include the Internet of Things, computer networking, cybersecurity, software-defined networking, machine learning, and deep learning.

NAZRUL HOQUE received the Ph.D. degree in computer science and engineering from Tezpur University, Tezpur, India, in 2017. He is currently an Assistant Professor with the Department of Computer Science, Manipur University, Canchipur, Imphal, India. He has published more than 40 papers in international journals and refereed conference proceedings. His research interests include machine learning, network security, and the Internet of Things.

KHUMUKCHAM ROBINDRO SINGH received the M.C.A. degree from Manipur University, Imphal, India, in 2007, and the Ph.D. degree in computer science from Gauhati University, Guwahati, India, in 2013. He joined as an Assistant Professor at the Department of Computer Science, Manipur University, in November 2014. He has led a significant research project in partnership with IIT Guwahati and Tezpur University, supported by MeitY, Government of India. He has organized two national workshops on high-performance computing with CDAC Pune and IIT Kharagpur under the National Supercomputing Mission, and also hosted the international "North East India AI Summit (NEIAIS 2025)" with funding from NEC, Shillong. He actively reviews for several esteemed international journals. His research interests include artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, expert systems, data structures, and object-oriented programming systems.

MONOWAR BHUYAN (Senior Member, IEEE) received the Ph.D. degree in computer science and engineering from Tezpur University, Assam, India, in 2014. Currently, he is an Associate Professor with the Department of Computing Science, Umeå University, Sweden, where he is also a Senior Member of the Autonomous Distributed Systems Laboratory (ADSLab). He has established and leads the Cyber Analytics and Learning Group. Prior to this, he worked at various academic institutions, including Nara Institute of Science and Technology, Nara, Japan, Assam Kaziranga University, Jorhat, India, and Umeå University, at different levels, from a Junior Scientist to an Associate Professor, from January 2009 to December 2019. He has an extensive publication record, with over 100 papers in the leading international journals and conference proceedings, and has written an advanced textbook on *Network Traffic Anomaly Detection and Prevention* (Springer). His experience leading/co-leading research projects attracted over 40 MSEK from national, European Commission, and international grant agencies. His research interests include machine learning, anomaly detection, systems and AI security, and distributed systems. He is a WASP Fellow.

...

LINTOINGAMBI TAKHELLAMBAM received the Master of Computer Applications (M.C.A.) degree from the Department of Computer Science, Manipur University, Canchipur, Imphal, Manipur, India, in 2021, where she is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree in the field of data privacy preservation and security of the IoT networks and leveraging federated learning. Her research interests include the Internet of Things, data privacy and security, machine learning, deep learning, and federated learning.